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**Liberation Philosophy in Marxian
Economics and its application to Shariah
Banking with reference to Indian
Banking System.**

**A Dissertation submitted in requirement of the Degree of M.A. in
Philosophy**

By

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Roll No. 21-PPL-009

UNDER THE GUIDANCE OF

Rev. Dr. Vinod Soreng SJ

06TH MARCH 2023

**THE DEPARTMENT OF PHILOSOPHY,
LOYOLA COLLEGE (AUTONOMOUS)
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I declare that the dissertation entitled, Liberation Philosophy in Marxian Economics and its application to Shariah Banking with reference to Indian Banking System, submitted by me for the Master's degree in philosophy is a work carried out by me during the period November 2022 to March 2023 under the guidance and supervision of Prof. Dr. Vinod Soreng, SJ. It is declared that no part of the thesis has been formed for the award of any degree, diploma, associate-ship, fellowship or any other similar titles prior to this date.

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I certify that the dissertation entitled, Liberation Philosophy in Marxian Economics and its application to Shariah Banking with reference to Indian Banking System, submitted for the Master's degree in philosophy by student SAVIO SALDANHA, is a work carried out during the period November 2022 to March 2023 under my guidance and supervision.

No part of the thesis has been submitted for the award of any degree, diploma, associate-ship, fellowship or any other similar titles prior to this date.

Chennai
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Prof. Dr. Vinod Soreng SJ
Supervisor

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Introduction

This paper is very close to my heart. I have worked in a public sector bank in India, and was honoured to have been posted in five different states in various positions, in semi-urban and rural branches. So, I did have a practical experience and knowledge about the problems faced by the Indian banking sector. I have been actually working on this paper for several years, but it was not a directed work. My efforts were haphazard and the method of proceeding was unclear. Only the objective was known to me, to study and come up with a constructive method to alleviate the problems faced by the Indian banking sector. In these two years of philosophical studies, I have learnt how to logically construct an argument and more importantly how to direct my thoughts in a constructive and precise manner. In this paper, "Liberation Philosophy in Marxian Economics and its application to Shariah Banking with reference to Indian Banking System," I have utilised these principles in a practical manner.

The Banking system in India was originally a private enterprise with a few corporate families and trusts owning the banks. This led them to finance their own business activities by raising funds. As such the access to banking facilities was limited to the upper class and select upper-middle class with majority of the Indian populace dependent on private money lenders who charged high rate of interest. This led to not only the economic exploitation of the population but also widening of the rich-poor divide in India. To overcome this problem the Government of India under Prime Minister Indira Gandhi undertook the Nationalization of 21 banks in India making banking accessible to everyone irrespective of their social class. This was in keeping up with the spirit of Indian Constitution which provides for equitable distribution of wealth and Socialist state of activities. As such the motto of the Public Sector Banks was to cater to the 'masses' and not the 'classes'. This does not mean that they did not finance businesses, but the priority was the common Indian citizen.

With the opening of Indian Economy to globalization and privatization, the structure of financial institutions across the nation saw a radical change. The advent of Multinational and private sector banking institutions led to a change of perspective of Indian banking sector. The ideal of making profit seemed lucrative and necessary to remain relevant according to the changing times and for the very survival of the banking organization. Banks began to cater and attract the corporate sector, the new-rich middle class and generation Y and Z, who had tremendous purchase power and whose activities were driving the Indian Economy.

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In this zeal to make profit and the rise of competition between the Public and Private sector banks, the masses [farmers and SME's (Small and Micro Enterprises)] began to lose. They seemed to be an unwanted drag in the quest of profit making (?). Rural branch posting was looked as 'punishment posting'.

I believe that the current state of the Indian banking system can be improved if it has a solid ethical foundation based upon the guiding principles and philosophy combining the Marxist economics and Shariah banking system. Now both these are considered as radical and opposing systems but they do not imply violence or tearing down of existing banking systems in India, rather, their usage will only help in cementing the ethical as well as the business aspect of our banking system and make it available for the entire population of our country.

As the term 'Shariah' suggests, it is based on the Islamic laws which are inscribed in the Holy Quran and the Hadith. However it does not imply that these are exclusively for the Muslims or the believers of the Quran, but everyone can benefit from the strong financial base the Shariah system of banking will provide.

Marxist economics may bring into mind the various revolutions and armed struggles between the labour and the bourgeoisie, but it should also be remembered that Marxian economic values are also the voice of the voiceless, the marginalised who are often overlooked in our zeal of profiteering. Hence, it is an important aspect if we want to provide a solid moral foundation to our banking system. Similarly, the philosophy of Marxist economy can further prevent the fundamentalist ideology taking over the Shariah banking and making it exclusive and limited to one particular religion to making it more inclusive and geared towards the holistic development of the entire society. In this paper I shall try to prove that although priority sector lending shows an increasing rate of NPAs, it will be absolutely dangerous for us to stop lending to this sector or make receiving loan more difficult by increasing the paperwork and formalities.

The aims and objectives of this paper can be summarized as follows, in the first chapter to understand the Indian Banking system with respect to its history, how and why it was nationalised and the effects of growing NPAs and which sector is to be blamed for it.

In the second chapter, I will elaborate the Shariah banking system with respect to its origin and philosophy, how it has contributed to the growth of economies around the world and how we can adapt it in the case of Indian financial sector.

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In the third chapter, I will elaborate the essential aspects of Marxian economy with reference to the economic doctrine of Marx, the liberation philosophy of Marxian economics and how we can adapt it to strengthen the Islamic banking system.

The fourth and final chapter; the philosophy of economics, I will bring the essential aspects of both the Marxist philosophy and the Shariah banking philosophy and present a new evolved model of banking for the Indian financial sector.

The thesis question I have taken up for this paper is, will a comprehensive study of Shariah banking from the Marxian economics perspective help to alleviate the problems of developing economies like India?

The Methodology I have employed in this paper is a qualitative analysis approach. I have used statistical data for proving some points but the analysis is qualitative.

In identifying the research gap, I have searched the internet for open resources on the topic which I have chosen and have discovered that although there has been a lot of research done separately on Marxian economics and Shariah banking system, the two have not been combined as a topic of research to my knowledge. Also I am looking at both from philosophical perspective towards the banking problems in India and not from any religious, cultural or ideological perspective.

CHAPTER ONE

An Introduction to banking and the problem of growing NPAs

In this Chapter, I shall discuss the fundamentals of my dissertation. I shall explain what is banking and a brief history of banking. I shall also explain the history of banking in India and the various types of banks present in India today. This chapter is important so as to understand the fundamentals of banking and to get an insight to the problem which shall be addressed during this paper, i.e. how the agriculture and the MSE is misrepresented as being the cause of NPA's in Indian Banking system.

1.1 What is banking?

Banks were born out of the necessity of mans' enterprising nature. As mankind moved out of the nomadic lifestyle and settled down into agrarian communities, more specialized occupations began to arise. The increase in population and the changes in standard of living meant that trade activities began within a tribe and with the neighbouring tribes. The traditional barter system was felt to be inadequate and currency was born out of the need to find a suitable standard for exchange of goods. The safety of keeping money while on travels was an utmost importance. The journey was unsafe due to a variety of reasons like robbers, and other natural conditions like floods and improper roads. This and other factors led to the rise of banks.

1.1.1 History of banking

Based on the recorded evidences the History of Banking can be traced to approximately 2000BC when merchants made loans for grains to the farmers and the traders started trading goods between the ancient cities of Assyria and Babylonia. The Code of Hammurabi, which dates back to approximately 1792-1750 BC, is one of the oldest deciphered writings recording significant details with respect to the social life during the period. In one part it deals with matters of contract and sets the terms of a transaction. This code also includes standardized procedures for handling loans, interest, and guarantees.

In later period, in ancient Greece and during the Roman Empire, we find money lenders based in temples that offered loans and started accepting deposits. We find the banking activities in ancient Greece to be more varied and sophisticated than in any previous society. These primitive bankers took deposits, made loans, changed money from one

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currency to another and tested coins for weight and purity. They even engaged in book transactions and maintained detailed records of their dealings in a systematic way. Moneylenders could also be found who would accept payment in one Greek city and arrange for credit in another, avoiding the need for the customer to transport or transfer large numbers of coins, thus making their trade activities more convenient.

Banking, as we understand it today, can be traced to medieval and early Renaissance Italy, to the merchant cities such as Florence, Venice, and Genoa. The development of banking spread throughout Europe and a number of important innovations took place in Amsterdam during the Dutch Republic in the 16th century and in London in the 17th century. Some of the earlier systems that facilitated trading and exchange of goods were barter system and gift economies (History of Banking, 2023).

1.1.2. The Evolution of Banking

Banking might have begun like this, but today the banking industry is one of the most complex and hugely diverse commercial enterprises offering a portfolio of a large number of financial services. Commercial banks are an important stimulant of the economy by managing institutional credit to their customers. Today; banks are large and complex organizations. Their clients range from individuals and corporate institutions, other banks, and governments of entire nations. Banking is a service industry, which means that they don't produce physical products but provide services to their clients. They deal with all types of money transactions, borrowing it, lending it, and many other related activities as I shall explain later.

1.1.3. Etymology of the term 'Bank'

The term bank apparently owes its origin to the "bank" or bench used by the money changers during the middle ages. Historically, there was a type of separation of banks based on the service they provided; example, some banks were called banks of deposit, and mainly held the deposits of foreign and domestic currencies and arranged payment in foreign trade transactions. Other banks created deposits that acted as a circulating medium of money in a society. One of the earliest banks in this category, the Bank of Venice, was formed when a group of the government's creditors combined and began using government debt as a means of payment in trade.

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1.1.4. The definitions of Banking

The definition of a bank varies from country to country. Under English common law, a banker is defined as ‘a person who carries on the business of banking, which is specified as conducting current accounts for his customers, paying cheques drawn on him, and collecting cheques for his customers’. Whereas in some legal texts in India, the banking company is defined as ‘the one which transacts the business of banking which means accepting, for the purpose of lending and investment of deposits of money from the public, repayable on demand or otherwise and withdrawals by cheques, draft, order or otherwise’.

1.1.5. Some notable definitions of Banking

“A banking company is the one which transacts the business of banking which means accepting, for the purpose of lending and investment of deposits of money from the public, repayable on demand or otherwise and withdrawals by cheques, draft, order or otherwise.”- Section 5(b) of the Banking Regulation Act; India.

"Banking means the accepting, for the purpose of lending or investment of deposits of money from the public, repayable on demand or otherwise and withdraw-able by cheque, draft, order or otherwise."- Section 5(b) of the Banking Regulation Act; India

1.1.6. Distinguishing Features of a Bank

From the above discussion, we can identify some of the distinguishing features of a bank, which can be highlighted as below:

1. The bank is an institution, which deals in money.
2. Acceptance of deposits of money from the public.
3. It mobilizes the savings of people.
4. In turn it lends or invests the money it so raised.
5. Profitable employment of such funds.
6. Makes funds available to businesses, financing their capital and revenue expenditure.
7. Provides financial services for a price i.e., interest, discount, commission, etc.
8. Not supposed to refund the money on its own accord.
9. For refunds, the depositor must make a proper demand for a refund of money through cheques, debit cards, online transfers or withdrawal slips.
10. Obligation to refund deposits on demand.
11. Deals in financial instruments.
12. Banking as the main business.

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13. A bank stimulates economic activity in the market by dealing in money (Definitions of Banking, 2023).

1.2. The evolution of Banks in India

Now we shall study the evolution of banks in India and their different categories and the impact of nationalized banks on its economy. I have divided this segment in three phases depending on the period of time.

Phase 1) The Pre-Independence Phase: The origin of banking activities in India can be traced back to the Vedic period of ancient India. At the time, money lending and borrowing were a few forms of banking activities. Manusmriti, an ancient legal text, has mentioned about money lending and rules regarding rates of interest (North, 2019).

There were almost 600 banks present in India before independence. The first bank to be established was the Bank of Hindustan was founded in 1770 in Calcutta. It closed down in 1832. The Oudh Commercial Bank was India's first commercial bank in the history of the evolution of banking in India. A few other banks that were established in the 19th century, such as Allahabad Bank (Est. 1865, now merged into Indian Bank effective from 1st April 2020) and Punjab National Bank (Est. 1894), have survived the test of time and exist even today. Some other banks like the Imperial Bank of Bengal, Imperial Bank of Madras, and the Imperial Bank of Bombay – established in the early to mid-1800s – were merged as one to become the Imperial Bank of India, which later became the State Bank of India.

Phase 2) The Post-Independence Phase: After independence, the evolution of the banking system in India continued pretty much the same as before. In 1969, the Government of India decided to nationalize the banks under the Banking Regulation Act, 1949. A total of 14 banks were nationalized, including the Reserve Bank of India (RBI). In 1975, the Government of India recognized that several groups were financially excluded. Between 1982 and 1990, it created banking institutions with specialized functions in line with the evolution of financial services in India.

NABARD (1982) – to support agricultural activities.

EXIM (1982) – to promote export and import.

National Housing Board – to finance housing projects.

SIDBI – to fund small-scale industries.

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Phase 3) The Modern Era (1991 till Date): From 1991 onwards, there was a sea change in the Indian economy. The government invited private investors to invest in India. Ten private banks were approved by the Reserve Bank of India. A few prominent names which exist even today from this liberalization are HDFC, Axis Bank, ICICI, DCB and IndusInd Bank. In the early to mid-2000s, two other banks, Kotak Mahindra Bank (2001) and Yes Bank (2004), received their licenses. IDFC and Bandhan banks were also given licenses in 2013-14.

Other notable changes and developments during this era were that foreign banks like Citibank, HSBC and Bank of America set up branches in India. The nationalization of banks came to a standstill.

1.2.2. Some reasons why banks were nationalized in India

To get a clearer picture of the impact of nationalization on the banking industry and the general population, let's understand why the government decided to nationalize banks.

The main objective was to secure the financial condition of the economy. Banks were collapsing at a fast rate approximately 361 banks failed between 1947 and 1955, which converts to about 40 banks a year! Customers lost their deposit with no chance of recovering them.

Agricultural Sector was neglected: Banks favoured large industries and businesses and neglected the rural sector. Nationalization came with a pledge to support the agricultural sector.

Expansion of Branches: Nationalization facilitated the opening of new branches to ensure maximum coverage of banks throughout the country. Every bank, be it government, private or multinational, had to open a percentage of their branches in rural area. This ensured the banks were able to cater to all segments of the society rather than limiting themselves to the profit-making metro and urban areas only.

Mobilization of Savings: Nationalizing the banks would allow people more access to banks and encourage them to save, injecting additional revenue into a cash-strapped economy. This would also ensure that the people would have their surplus cash secured and profitable by the way of earning interest on their savings.

Economic and Political Factors: The two wars in 1962 and 1965 had put a tremendous burden on the economy. The nationalization of Indian banks would give the economy a boost through increased deposits. This is the way national banks work, by lending out the deposit received at higher rate of interest to other individuals or institutions including the government.

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To energize priority sectors: To enable agriculture and MSME sector to receive funds so as to develop these sectors. They are still notified as ‘priority sector’ and all banks have to finance a percentage of these sectors from their total advance exposure. The failure to comply with these requirements leads to banks being penalized and repeated failure can even lead to the banking license of the company being revoked. However the banks have devised a simple loophole to evade this by window dressing certain loan products like gold loan to farmers as agriculture loans and other methods.

1.2.3. The Positive Effects of Nationalization

The nationalization of Indian banks was one of the most significant events in the evolution of banks in India. Today, India has 12 nationalized banks. Here are a few ways that nationalization benefited the economy:

Increased Savings: There was a sharp increase in savings with the opening of new branches. As national income rose in the 1970s, gross domestic savings almost doubled.

Improved Efficiency: The efficiency of banks improved with additional accountability. It also increased public confidence.

Empowering SSIs: Small scale industries (SSIs) received a boost resulting in a proportionate improvement in the economy.

Financial Inclusion: The overall statistics of the banking sector and the Indian economy showed a marked improvement. It reflected on parameters like the share of bank deposits to GDP, gross savings rate, the share of advances to DGP, and gross investment rate from 1969 to 1991.

Better Outreach: Banks were now no longer only restricted to metropolitan areas. Branches were opened in the remotest corners of the country.

A Surge in Public Deposits: The increased reach of banks helped small industries, agriculture, and the export sector grow. This growth was accompanied by a proportionate increase in public deposits.

The Green Revolution: One of the biggest priority items on the government’s agenda received a boost thanks to the support that the newly-nationalized banks provided to the agricultural sector.

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1.2.4. Drawbacks of Nationalization

To provide an unbiased view on the subject, here are a few downsides of nationalization:

Socio-Economic Challenges: The banks couldn't provide sufficient support to eradicate poverty or provide adequate financing to the grassroots levels of society. This was particularly obvious in rural India. The idea that rural branches of nationalized banks and other banks would cater to the populace with no access to the banking sector remained a dream one of the reason being that the banks did not have any special products to offer which were tailor made for the rural people. These people could not provide documentation or match the repayment schedules, or provide security, as the urban and metro people could and this proved to be a big hassle in order to cater to them more effectively.

Competition from Private Banks: Despite government support and increased impetus through a rise in deposits, public sector banks were never able to surpass private banks in performance. This was mainly due to the fact that only cosmetic changes were made in the way of their operations, the hierarchical model and little attention was paid to the fact as why the private sector banks were so efficient in their way of operations (e.g. Back office processes to reduce the work load of the branch staff and aggressive marketing strategies).

Failure to Achieve Financial Inclusion: Although financial inclusion was the major objective of nationalizing banks, it was not adequately enabled. It was only achieved to a limited extent after the launch of a government campaign called Jan Dhan Yojana (Evolution of Banking in India, 2022). This scheme was simply a rebranding to existing product with the nationalized banks called 'Zero-balance-Saving Account' or 'Small Savings Account'. The reason why it became popular as Jan-Dhan Account is because of falsified promises by the government of each account receiving ₹.15, 00,000/- during electoral campaigns. Also the banks were given strict targets based on the population under their region of control.

1.3. The Structure/ Types of Banks in India

In this article, I shall explain the banking structure in India and how different banks are classified as per the RBI Norms. The Indian banking industry has been divided into two parts, organized and unorganized sectors. The organized sector consists of Reserve Bank of India, Commercial Banks and Co-operative Banks, and Specialized Financial Institutions (IDBI, ICICI, IFC, etc.). The unorganized sector, which is not homogeneous, is largely made up of money lenders and indigenous bankers. I shall explain in detail the difference between

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nationalized banks, scheduled banks, public sector banks, private banks, and foreign banks, i.e. the types of banks prevalent in India.

One might ask as why we have so many types of classifications or is there the need of so many different types of financial institutions. The answer to this question is that as the focus of banking is varied, the needs are also diverse and methods different. Banking institutions offer an assortment of services from deposits in savings accounts to housing and business loans to check clearing, underwriting, and credit cards. The world is changing fast and globalization in conjunction with technological advances is changing the landscape of the banking industry. Both individuals and business customers are demanding faster and innovative products & services. The banking industry is also heavily regulated and has its own share of challenges to deliver financial objectives to people and organizations. Thus, distinctive kinds of banks are evolving to cater to various business demands, social needs, and global complexities. Different banking institutions conduct their operations in a different manner. Hence the banks can be classified in a variety of ways, according to applicable law and regulations, based on their domicile, on basis of ownership, on basis of function and structure.

1.3.1. The Classification of the Indian Banks

For the purpose of this paper, I shall be presenting classification as applicable in India. The majority of banks are regulated by the Central Bank of the country (e.g. for India it is the Reserve Bank of India). The Indian Banks can be classified as below:

1.3.1.1. Central Banks.

Every country has a Central Bank of its own which is generally regulated by a special act. Central banks are bankers' banks, i.e. they act as bankers for the banks in that nation and also for the government. These banks trace their history from the Bank of England. It is called a Central Bank because it occupies a central position in the banking system acting as the highest financial authority and controller of credit in the country. The main function of this bank is to regulate and supervise the whole banking system in the country. This bank guarantees stable monetary and financial policy from country to country and play an important role in the economy of the country. Typical functions of these banks include implementing monetary policy, managing foreign exchange and gold reserves, making decisions regarding official interest rates, acting as banker to the government and other banks, and regulating and supervising the banking industry. These banks buy government

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debt, have a monopoly on the issuance of paper money, and often act as a lender of last resort to commercial banks. The Central bank of any country supervises controls and regulates the activities of all the commercial banks of that country. It controls and coordinates the currency and credit policies of any country.

In India, the Reserve Bank of India is the central bank. It is the apex bank and the statutory institution in the money market of the country.

1.3.1.2. Scheduled & Non-Scheduled Banks

Scheduled Banks in India are those banks which have been included in the Second Schedule of Reserve Bank of India (RBI) Act, 1934. RBI in turn includes only those banks in this schedule which satisfy the criteria laid down vide section 42 (6) (a) of the Act. As of 30 June 1999, there were 300 scheduled banks in India having a total network of 64,918 branches. Scheduled commercial banks in India include State Bank of India and its associates (5), nationalized banks (12), foreign banks (46), private sector banks (21), co-operative banks and regional rural banks. 'Scheduled banks in India' means the State Bank of India constituted under the State Bank of India Act, 1955 (23 of 1955), a subsidiary bank as defined in the State Bank of India (Subsidiary Banks) Act, 1959 (38 of 1959), a corresponding new bank constituted under section 3 of the Banking Companies (Acquisition and Transfer of Undertakings) Act, 1970 (5 of 1970), or under section 3 of the Banking Companies (Acquisition and Transfer of Undertakings) Act, 1980 (40 of 1980), or any other bank being a bank included in the Second Schedule to the Reserve Bank of India Act, 1934 (2 of 1934), but does not include a co-operative bank. Scheduled banks have paid-up capital and reserves of the value of not less than Rs 5 lakhs and are eligible for loans and other privileges from the central bank like membership to the clearing-house. RBI has no specific control over non-scheduled banks as they are not included in the second schedule of RBI Act, 1934.

Scheduled banks can be further classified as:

Public Sector

Private Sector

Foreign Banks

Regional Rural Banks

Co-operative Banks

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1.4. What are the Non Performing Assets (NPA) in banking?

Since the liberalization of the economy in 1991, the Indian banking sector has undergone a dramatic shift from the absolute monopoly of public sector banks to the entry of private and foreign banks. Despite the fact that the Indian banking industry is heavily regulated and supervised by Reserve Bank of India (RBI), it still faces a number of ethical and corporate governance issues.

As we know the manner of operation of a bank to generate income is by accepting deposits from the investors at a said rate of interest. This deposit is then provided as loan to borrowers on an increased rate of interest. The difference between the two is the profit. Example, Bank receives ₹.100 from a depositor; it agrees to pay him ₹.4 as interest for one year. The bank will hence pay the depositor ₹.104 after the period of one year. Before lending this ₹.100 to others, the bank will have to keep a certain amount as security with the Central Bank of the country (RBI in India) as liquidity security [Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR) and Statutory Liquidity Ratio (SLR)] (RBI, 2022). Suppose it is ₹.20, the bank now has ₹.80 to lend to borrowers. It will then lend ₹.80 at a rate of interest of say, 9% for one year. Hence after one year the borrower will repay ₹. 87 to the bank. It will also get some interest on the CRR and SLR kept with the RBI, say ₹.1. Hence, the bank now has ₹.108; it will give ₹.104 to the depositor as agreed and get a profit of ₹.4 in this transaction. For getting this profit it is important for the borrower to repay the loan on time. But suppose if he defaults to pay, then the bank will have to pay the depositor from its own profits or borrow from RBI. Regular defaults will mean decrease in profits and even the bank going bankrupt. These defaulting loans are called as Non Performing Assets (NPA). Hence we can say that the NPAs are the advances or loans given by the banks which have stopped being an asset to it.

According to paragraph 2.1 of RBI Master Circular RBI/2013-14/62 DBOD. No. BP. BC., 1/ 21.04.048/ 2013-14 dated July 01, 2013 addressed to all Commercial Banks (excluding RRBs) on Prudential norms on Income Recognition, Asset Classification and Provisioning pertaining to Advances, Non-Performing Assets is defined as under:

1.4.2. Non Performing Assets

An asset, including a leased asset, becomes non performing when it ceases to generate income for the bank. A non-performing asset (NPA) is a loan or an advance where interest and or instalment of principal remain overdue for a period of more than 90 days in respect of a term loan (loan given on a fixed term). The account remains 'out of order' in respect of an Overdraft/Cash Credit (OD/CC), the bill remains overdue for a period of more than 90 days in

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the case of bills purchased and discounted, the instalment of principal or interest thereon remains overdue for two crop seasons for short duration crops, the instalment of principal or interest thereon remains overdue for one crop season for long duration crops, the amount of liquidity facility remains outstanding for more than 90 days, in respect of a securitization transaction undertaken, in respect of derivative transactions, the overdue receivables representing positive mark-to-market value of a derivative contract, if these remain unpaid for a period of 90 days from the specified due date for payment. In case of interest payments, banks should, classify an account as NPA only if the interest due and charged during any quarter is not serviced fully within 90 days from the end of the quarter. In addition, an account may also be classified as NPA in terms of paragraph 4.2.4 of this Master Circular. An account should be treated as 'out of order' if the outstanding balance remains continuously in excess of the sanctioned limit/drawing power.

In cases where the outstanding balance in the principal operating account is less than the sanctioned limit/drawing power, but there are no credits continuously for 90 days as on the date of Balance Sheet or credits are not enough to cover the interest debited during the same period, these accounts should be treated as 'out of order'. Any amount due to the bank under any credit facility is 'overdue' if it is not paid on the due date fixed by the bank.

1.4.2.1. Accounts with temporary deficiencies

The classification of an asset as NPA should be based on the record of recovery. Bank should not classify an advance account as NPA merely due to the existence of some deficiencies which are temporary in nature such as non-availability of adequate drawing power based on the latest available stock statement, balance outstanding exceeding the limit temporarily, non-submission of stock statements and non-renewal of the limits on the due date, etc. In the matter of classification of accounts with such deficiencies banks may follow the following guidelines:

Banks should ensure that drawings in the working capital accounts are covered by the adequacy of current assets, since current assets are first appropriated in times of distress. Drawing power is required to be arrived at based on the stock statement which is current. However, considering the difficulties of large borrowers, stock statements relied upon by the banks for determining drawing power should not be older than three months. The outstanding in the account based on drawing power calculated from stock statements older than three months, would be deemed as irregular. A working capital borrowed account will become

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NPA if such irregular drawings are permitted in the account for a continuous period of 90 days even though the unit may be working or the borrower's financial position is satisfactory. Regular and ad hoc credit limits need to be reviewed/ regularized not later than three months from the due date/date of ad hoc sanction. In case of constraints such as non-availability of financial statements and other data from the borrowers, the branch should furnish evidence to show that renewal/ review of credit limits is already on and would be completed soon. In any case, delay beyond six months is not considered desirable as a general discipline. Hence, an account where the regular/ ad hoc credit limits have not been reviewed/ renewed within 180 days from the due date/ date of ad hoc sanction will be treated as NPA. In short NPA is defined as an asset, including a leased asset, becomes non-performing when it ceases to generate income for the bank. A non-performing asset (NPA) is defined as a credit facility in respect of which the interest and/or instalment of principal has remained 'past due' for specified period of time (90 days, March 31, 2004 onwards).

1.4.3. The causes and effects of growing NPAs on the Indian economy

I have discussed in the previous segment the technicalities and the modalities of NPAs and why and when loans become NPAs. Now let us discuss the effects of NPAs on the economy of a country, particularly India.

i. The Causes of growing NPAs

The growth of NPAs is a threat to the Indian banking system and the Indian economy as whole. The Indian private and public sector banks are equal contributors to corporate debts, but according to the Financial Stability Report June 2016, the public sector has more serious NPAs than the private sector banks. The root causes of the higher NPAs in PSBs is the political influence and corruption that helps large corporations for sanctioning and waiving off the loans, least accountability on the board members of PSBs, lax nature of the PSBs employees and administration (Harani & Mutyala, 2019). Therefore, lately the government proposed to privatize some of the major public sector banks for reducing stressed assets. This latest trend of privatization goes against the thought process of public welfare which resulted in the nationalization of the banks in 1969. Instead of understanding the root causes of growing NPAs and taking strict remedial measures, the government seems to wash its hands off its responsibility. There is a common failure to understand that only the government owned PSBs will be able to cater to the poor and the marginalized while privatizing them will only cause the disfranchisement and alienation of the majority of poor Indians.

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The NPAs of priority and non-priority sectors from FY 2010 to 2017, the non-priority sectors performed poorly throughout the selected years. Despite of these evidences the banks extend loans quite easily to the non-priority sectors (Goyal, 2020; Mohanty, 2020). The rapid growth of NPA is also the result of over dependence of corporate sector on PSBs mainly because they provide advances on lesser rate of interests. The banks also rely on non-priority sectors to earn interest income than on priority sectors because as the ticket size of corporate advances is high; it also means that the interest earned is correspondingly high.

NPAs in non-priority sectors are likely to increase due to decelerating trends in major sectors like manufacturing and infrastructure and slowing down of economy during 2012. They were also of the view that the factor contributing to the rising NPAs is the upward shift in interest rates due to the RBI's tight money policy for controlling inflation. The increased interest rate (floating interest) has increased the repayment burden of borrowers which is compelling them to default their interest payments and repayments. They also feel that the banks should focus on recovery of existing loans and be more circumspect in their credit appraisal, rescheduling of large corporate loans as rising interest cost and falling sales revenue may result in widespread defaults of corporate loans, phasing out of priority sector loans to 10% of the total loans so as to reduce the burden of NPAs in priority sector, making priority sector loans need based rather than target based which results in poor credit appraisal and loan default.

Mr. Gunjan M. Sanjeev has attempted to identify the critical factors, which were responsible for the loans to go bad in the Indian commercial banking system. The study had used primary data collected from credit managers of banks operating in India. His study has revealed that the external factors have a higher influence compared to the internal factors Economic downturn and willful default; have been found to be most critical. Poor credit scoring skill of managers, absence of suitable administrative penalties and target completion have been found to have a significant influence amongst factors related with the loan appraisal mechanism. Seizure and disposal of collateral have found to be the toughest challenges amongst the factors related with the loan monitoring and controlling mechanism. Loan manger's level of motivation, manpower, skill to appraise collateral, effort to reduce costs, government and political intervention and soft budget constraints have been found to have a lower influence.

Shivpuje C.V. and Kaveri V.S. states that the study was basically confined to identifying the factors influencing NPAs, suggesting measures that would prevent the growth of NPAs and affect their speedy recovery. The major emphasis was laid on internal factors

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over which banks and financial institutions have direct control. For this purpose, they surveyed a few branches, had interaction with the branch managers and the borrowers along with the study of inspection reports. In addition, discussions were held with the credit officers, law officers, executives, bank lawyers, and civil judges. Along with this, the secondary data was analyzed to find out the various dimensions of NPAs. They concluded that NPA problem could be solved if proper care of internal factors is taken or in other words recovery from NPAs is possible if efforts of the bank and financial institutions are strengthened. They observed that though the branch managers were quite clear about the RBI guidelines on the classification of advances, they varied the actual classification of advances made by them based on their personal experience with different borrowers. This trend, in particular, was observed in trading accounts with persisting irregularity in cash credit account for a long time. They noted that eight branch managers included the said account in the health code no.2 while six managers classified it under the code no.4. In the end they had also offered several suggestions calling for changes in internal systems, procedures and practices (Korde & Laghate, 2014). This is because the internal rating system is not objective but depends on the perspective of the advances officer processing the loan. Experienced officers tend to be easier going than the new officers, also few can be manipulated by internal or external pressures or inducements to provide favourable reports neglecting or skipping over the anomalies in the balance sheet of the corporate.

ii. The effects of NPA on the Indian Economy

The Indian banking sector accounts for a major portion of financial intermediation and is considered to be the main channel of monetary policy transmission, credit delivery and payment systems. The stability and sound health of the banking system hence is a key pre-requisite for overall economic development and financial stability. The Non-Performing Assets (NPA) is an important prudential indicator to assess the financial health of the banking sector. Besides asset quality, NPAs epitomize the credit risk management and efficacy in the allocation of resources.

The accelerating rate of NPAs in Indian banking system has been prevailing since it was recognized officially on the recommendations of Narasimham Committee in 1991. The recommendations of this committee once enforced mandated that a certain provisioning be made from the banks own profit, for the stress assets. Stress assets mean the loans which have not yet become NPAs but are showing some signs of slipping into the segment. In addition to the stress assets, banks were also obliged to make provisioning for the accounts which have

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already become NPAs based on the duration of the account being labelled as NPAs. The stressed assets in the books of banks are mostly the result of corporate defaults. Recently, the NPAs have been mounting due to the multiple factors such as the increasing number of willful defaulters, the strict NPA recognition norms and economic slowdown caused due to the outbreak of COVID-19. However, the RBI and Government of India have taken measure to contain the swelling NPA in the form of recovery regime, time-bound resolution of bankrupt entities, re-capitalization of PSBs, merger, reorganization and privatization of PSBs. Despite all the efforts, government is not able succeed satisfactorily although the IBC Code 2016 did perform well by recovering 61% of the total recovery made during 2018-19.

There is a near unanimity among the economists that asset quality is a critical determinant of sound functioning of the banking system. NPAs affect the operational efficiency, which in turn affects profitability, liquidity and solvency position of banks (Michael et al., 2006). The consequences of NPAs would be reduction in interest income, high level of provisioning, stress on profitability, gradual decline in ability to meet steady increase in cost, increased pressure on net interest margin (NIM) thereby reducing competitiveness, steady erosion of capital resources and increased difficulty in augmenting capital resources (Batra, 2003). The asset quality problems could be contagious, insidious and they prey on the weak. The contagious nature of loan losses emanates from the fact that their downside impact can quickly transmit to earnings, capital, and liquidity. They are insidious in the sense that it is often difficult to know that there is a problem until it's too late. Moreover, these problems prey on the weak banks, which are vulnerable and have relatively small amounts of capital to absorb unanticipated losses. NPAs generate a vicious cycle of effects on the sustainability and growth of the banking system, and if not managed properly could lead to bank failures.

Empirical evidence indicates a relationship between bank failures and higher NPAs worldwide (Chijoriga, 2000; Dash & Kabra, 2010). The links between financial crises and bank funding may be strongest during banking crises. Such crises tend to arise primarily from deteriorating economic fundamentals, notably declines in asset quality (Borio & Lowe, 2002). The issue is of particular importance after the recent global financial crisis and the failure of some large institutions and bailouts that followed. In the Indian context also empirical research suggests that asset quality is one of the main determining factors of credit, besides time deposits and lending interest rate (RBI, 2008).

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1.5. Can Agriculture and MSEs be blamed for the growing NPAs in Indian Banking Sector?

One study was conducted by Khushpat S. Jain and Rahul G. Chopra whose objective was to analyze the trends in NPAs in the Indian Banking Sector from 2004-2011, to assess the contributing factors to the NPA in the Indian Banking Sector and to suggest measures to halt and curtail the rising burden of NPAs, the authors mainly dealt with the rising burden of NPAs in Indian financial system and their likely impact and measures to minimize such adverse impact on the Indian banking system in particular and Indian economy in general. The authors arrived at a conclusion that the major contributor to the NPAs in banking sector was agricultural sector. This conclusion according to me is highly biased as the data collected by the RBI and majority other researches conclusively disprove their conclusion. Let us look at a chart showing the contribution of different sectors to the NPAs. This chart is compiled from the data collected from the RBI website.

Sources: RBI

As seen from above the Non-priority sector has the higher contribution to the NPAs. Since the year 2000, the share of priority sector in total NPAs has averaged at 45 per cent, while the share of non-priority sector averaged at 55 per cent. Prior to the period of 2008, the share of priority sector in total NPAs was expanding, while that of non-priority sector was declining in line with the general decline in total NPAs. Disaggregated analysis reveals that, on an average, retail loans occupy the largest share in total NPAs followed by small scale industries (SSIs), agriculture, personal loans, housing loans, exports, credit cards and auto loans. This data includes agriculture and SSIs as a part of the priority sector which includes home loans, auto loans, personal loans etc.

Let us study the percentage of agriculture loans in priority sector. The disaggregated analysis of priority sector shows that over the last one decade, the average share of agriculture in total NPAs remains lower than the share of SSIs and other priority sectors

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However, the share of agriculture and other priority sectors in aggregate NPAs increased, while that of SSIs declined during the post crisis period.

The recent years have witnessed increased credit flow to agriculture. The share of agriculture in total gross advances increased from 10.5 per cent in the 2001-07 period to 12.3 per cent in the 2008-12 period. The increase in credit flow to SSI sector was relatively lower in the 2008-12 period. However, in respect of other priority sectors, even while the share in gross advances came down, their share in aggregate NPAs increased during the 2008-12 period. The growth in credit flow to agriculture accelerated significantly during 2002-06, averaging at around 28 percent per annum, before decelerating thereafter to over 22 per cent per annum, during 2007-12. The high growth in agriculture credit during the 2001-07 period could be attributed to the program of doubling of credit flow to agriculture that was launched by the Government for the period 2004-05 to 2006-07. The growth in NPAs in agriculture, which was negative up to the year 2006, rose significantly by end-March 2008. The growth in NPAs in agriculture declined sharply in 2009 due to the implementation of the Agriculture Debt Waiver and Relief Scheme, 2008 (RBI, 2010). In the recent years, however, the growth in NPAs in agriculture has been high, averaging at over 28 per cent during 2007-2012. In fact, the growth in NPAs in agriculture was as high as 61 per cent by the end of March 2011, although it decelerated subsequently to 49 per cent by end-March 2012. The high growth in credit to agricultural sector during the pre-crisis period might have contributed to the growth in agricultural NPAs in the subsequent years owing to the deterioration in credit quality.

The credit growth to SSIs sector witnessed a marked acceleration, before the crisis period of 2008, averaging at over 19 per cent. This period also saw negative growth in NPAs in SSI sector. In the 2008-12 period, the credit growth to SSIs sector decelerated, but remained higher than the 2001-07 period, averaging at over 22 percent. However, the growth in NPAs, which was negative before 2008, increased significantly thereafter, averaging at around 31 per cent. Even the data for Micro and Small Enterprises (MSEs) for 2011 and 2012; show that the NPAs grew sharply at 24 percent. The rise in the growth of NPAs in the SSI sector was partly a reflection of the impact of the financial crisis and the economic

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slowdown that had set in thereafter. Thus, NPAs in SSIs sector have also contributed to rise in aggregate NPAs in the recent years (Lokare, 2014)

Now, I would like to draw your attention to the fact that the data I have received from RBI and other sources paints a rather grim picture about the growing NPAs in agriculture and SSIs. Although there is a trend of increase in the percentage of the NPAs in these two sectors, the fact that the data speaks in terms of percentage rather than the actual figures must be taken into consideration. In most of the parts of our country the ticket size of agriculture loan is very small, to the extent of ₹.10000/-. Now, here lies the manipulative nature of statistics being put before us, in ₹.1000000/- I can safely finance say 90-100 farmers, while the same amount can be given to a single corporate customer. Now, as our assets are well spread over 90-100 farmers and even if 10 of them don't repay, I won't lose much sleep as the exposure of risk will be ₹.100000/- or 10% of our total advances. But if the single corporate customer defaults then the entire advance amount becomes an NPA. However, statistics revealed to us would say that while only 1% corporate loans become NPA, 10% of agriculture loans became NPA in the same time! Hence, I say that we should not believe the half-truth of high percentage of agriculture loans becoming NPAs.

Some economic strategists like Khushpat S. Jain and Rahul G. Chopra suggest that we should make priority sector loans need-based rather than target-based which results in poor credit appraisal and loan default. Again, although not entirely false, but we must ask ourselves, if target is not allotted for priority sector like agriculture and SSIs, will these sectors be able to get loans when they need them the most? How are we going to judge a case is actually need based, because as I have already explained, our loan processing is not completely objective but rather depends a lot on the officer processing the loan. Will we be able to place an objective and well monitored mechanism to see if priority sector advances are being disbursed on a proper need based perspective? On this, I have not been able to find any suggestion.

Conclusion

I conclude hereby that although priority sector lending show increasing rate of NPAs, it will be absolutely dangerous for us to stop lending to this sector or make receiving loan more difficult by increasing the paperwork and formalities. We should keep in mind the visionary mindset of our leaders in 1969 when they nationalized few Indian banks. Nationalization was a safe and sure way to keep a complete check on banking activities as well as to ensure that the benefits of government schemes reached their beneficiaries. In

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doing so it was a common knowledge that these banks would have to sacrifice their profits for the good of the society as whole. With the change of times, although profit making is the need of the times to keep our banks healthy and matching the global standards of banking, we should also keep in mind that India is a unique country with almost 58% people still dependent on agriculture and allied activities and their interests must be given equal importance if not precedence in any and all decision making process. Similarly, SSI/MSE sector holds a key to providing employment for millions of our population especially the youth and can be our biggest strength in producing products which are in demand on national and global level, hence even this sector should not be ignored.

A proper planned approach is required and hand holding measures are needed while dealing with these sectors. Also, special products (advances and deposits) need to be tailor made for these sectors which are flexible and customer friendly in nature. We have to decide if standard one-size fits all approach in categorizing them NPA is indeed logical or can we introduce different measurement criteria for them?

Similarly, I also feel very strongly that we need an ethical based banking approach based on Shariah and Marxist philosophies. These will ensure that Indian banking sector does not lose its focus on the needy while chasing profit. We shall discuss the same in the following chapters.

Chapter Two

The Shariah banking system.

2. An Introduction to the Islamic Banking system.

In the earlier chapter I have discussed the system of banking and brought out the concept of banking in its definition, development of the banks in the world and in India, the different types of banks and the challenges in the agriculture and MSE sector financing. I have tried to bring out how the priority sector especially the Agriculture and the MSE is unfairly targeted as the causes of the growing NPAs in India and how the authorities have tried to solve this by privatizing the Nationalized banks which will prove to be a fatal mistake in our endeavour to be an inclusive economy.

The aim of this chapter is to understand the Shariah Banking and I shall try to explain the fact that how it transcends the Islamic law in the religious sense and can be used to provide a solid moral base for the Indian banking system.

2.1. What is the Shariah banking system?

Islamic banking, also known as Islamic finance or Shariah-compliant finance, refers to financial activities that are compliant to Shariah (Islamic law). Two fundamental principles of Islamic banking are the sharing of profit and loss and the prohibition of the collection and payment of interest by lenders and investors. Islamic banking is rooted in the tenets of the Islamic faith as mentioned in the Quran regarding commercial transactions. The principles of Islamic banking are derived from the Quran which is the central religious text of Islam. In Islamic banking, all transactions must comply with Shariah which is the legal code of Islam (based on the teachings of the Quran). The rules that govern commercial transactions in Islamic banking are referred to as *fiqh al-muamalat*. The employees of institutions that abide by Islamic banking are trusted to not deviate from the fundamental principles of the Quran while they are conducting business. When more information or guidance is necessary, Islamic bankers turn to learned scholars or use independent reasoning based on scholarship and customary practices (Tarver, 2022).

The important fact which should also be mentioned here is that the employees of Islamic banks while working according to the principles of the Islamic teachings are not required to be practicing Muslims themselves, hence, they can belong to other religions or non-religious, there is no rule regarding the personal faith of the employee of the Islamic

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bank. What is required is the basic understanding of the teachings of the Quran which in turn guides the daily working of the organization.

2.1.1. The development of the Shariah Banking system.

Islamic economics as we know today has its roots in early history of Muslims. Besides, the Qur'an and Hadith, the two primary sources of Islamic economics, which have always ignited the imagination of the Muslim scholars, we have reliable information on various treatises on public finance, distribution of war booty, zakah administration and land management. However, some writers of later centuries wrote about trade and markets as well. The most prominent of these books are Kitab al-Kharaj by Abu Yusuf (113-183 AH¹), Kitab al-Isharah ila Mahasin at-Tijarah wa Marifat Jayyid al-A'rad wa Kadiiha wa Ghush-ush al-Mudallisin fiha (A Guide to the Merits of Commerce and to Recognition of Both Fine and Defective Merchandise and the Swindles of Those Who Deal Dishonestly) by Abu al-Fadl Ja'afar al-Dimashqi (12th century AD), al-Hisba fil Islam and al-Siyasah al-Shari'yya by Ibn Taymiyya (1263-1328 AD), Al-Muqaddima by Ibn Khaldun (1332-1404 AD), Hujjat Allah al-Baligha (The Profound Evidence of Allah) by Shah Waliullah (1703-1762 AD). Earlier writers focused on public finance but later ones, particularly Ibn Khaldun and Shah Waliullah, discussed the question of rise and fall of nations and development of civilization over long period.

After these earlier works, the Muslims went into intellectual slumber from fifteenth century and by advent of the nineteenth century the entire Muslim world was subjugated to the West. With political subservience came intellectual stupor. We do not find any significant contribution by Muslims while the West was experiencing the Renaissance. The torch of knowledge passed on from Muslims of Spain to the Christian West. The Islamic world which was once an open-minded and a progressive society became more orthodox and lost its scientific and philosophical edge over the rest of the world. It became a religious and more of a cultic society. Thus, the Muslims were losing ground on political, economic, social fronts to colonialists around the world.

In nineteenth century when movements for political freedom started in various parts of the Muslim world, some thinkers raised voice for going back to the roots of Islam, for intellectual inspiration. The immediate concern was that the Western knowledge with its anti-

¹ The first day of Year One of the Islamic calendar was set as the first day of the Hijrah, the Prophet's migration from Makkah to Madinah on July 26, 622 C.E. The western convention in designating Islamic dates is thus by the abbreviation AH, which stands for the Latin Anno Hegirae, or 'Year of the Hijrah'. <https://catstevens.com/think/spiritual-domain/understanding-the-islamic-calendar>.

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religious and secular outlook would drag the Muslim populace away from its primary sources. Most prominent of these thinkers were Syed Ahmad Khan (1817-98), Muhammad Abduh (1849-1905), Jamaluddin Afghani (1839-1897), Rashid Rida (1865-1935) and Muhammad Iqbal (1877-1938). They raised voice for a critical look at the Western knowledge. However, none of them actually used the term 'Islamic economics', although they criticized capitalism for its injustices.

The twentieth century saw gradual freedom of Muslim lands from the colonialist rulers. That inspired some bright intellectuals of the Muslim world who invited people for revival of Islam both at the level of state and at individual levels. This movement was spear-headed by religious such scholars as Hasan al-Banna (d. 1949), Syed Qutb (d. 1966), Muhammad Rafiuddin (d. 1969), Abu al-'Ala Mawdudi (d. 1979), Muhammad Baqir al-Sadr (d. 1980), and Isma'il Raji al-Faruqi (d.1986). These scholars emphasized need for Islamic economic system and Islamization of knowledge. Their powerful writings inspired many Muslim scholars, professionals, and economists who felt need for developing Islamic economics as a social science. Most prominent of these scholars are M.N. Siddiq, Khurshid Ahmad, Umer Chapra, Anas Zarqa, Monzer Kahf, Fahim Khan, Ma'abid al-Jarhi, Murat Cizakca, Mehmet only a few of them. Joining of economists like Asutay, Kabir Hassan, Munawar Iqbal, Abbas Mirakhor, Zamir Iqbal, and Hasan Askari, to mention a few of them, in the revivalist movement gave strong impetus to the development of Islamic economics as a social science. People started hearing the slogan of Islamic economics as panacea for economic ills of capitalism and socialism.

The watershed came in 1976 with the First International Conference on Islamic Economics held in Makkah (Saudi Arabia) under the auspices of King Abdulaziz University, Jeddah. Several hundred Muslim scholars, economists, bankers and academicians gathered and asserted their will for creating 'Islamic economics' as social science. It led to establishment of Centre for Research in Islamic Economics (now re-named as Institute of Islamic Economics). Simultaneously, the movement for Islamic revival created an impetus for interest-free finance, since interest was perceived as source of all economic ills of the capitalist system. Again, Saudi Arabia played leadership role in establishing Islamic Development Bank in 1975. The Bank also set up its think-tank in the form of Islamic Research and Training Institute. Both these Institutes are still leaders in Islamic economics, although several others have sprung up in various parts of the world. Most prominent objective of these organizations is to develop alternative academic discipline in the name of Islamic economics (Khan, 2016).

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2.1.2. The basics of Islamic Banking in the Quran, Hadith and Fiqh.

Riba or ‘interest’ is considered as Haram in Islamic finance. This is the most important point in it. No interest can be charged on activities which involve lending money. Hence it is very important for us to understand the context in which it appears in the Islamic scripture and revered texts.

Among the most important teachings of Islam for establishing justice and eliminating exploitation in business transactions is the prohibition of all sources of ‘unjustified enrichment’ (Akl Amwal al nas bi al batil). The Quran and the sunnah have given principles whereby Muslim society can know or deduce what constitutes a ‘wrongful or rightful’ and ‘justified or unjustified’ source of earning or acquisition of property from others. One of the important sources of unjustified earning is receiving any monetary advantage in business transaction without giving a just counter value. Riba represents, in the Islamic value system, a prominent source of unjustified advantage. The following verses from the Quran and Hadith throw light on Riba as a source of unjustified advantage in business transactions.

2.1.2.1. Riba in the Qur’an.

The most Holiest of Islamic texts is the Quran and it specifically prohibits Riba, I shall emphasize on the texts which mention Riba in the sequential order as they appear in the Quran (Translated by Yusuf Ali, 2000).

1. **First Revelation (Surah al-Rum, Verse 39)** states that, ‘that which you give as interest to increase the peoples’ wealth increases not with God; but that which you give in charity, seeking the goodwill of God, multiplies manifold’.

2. **Second Revelation (Surah al-Nisa, Verse 161)** states that, ‘And for their taking interest even though it was forbidden for them, and their wrongful appropriation of other people’s property. We have prepared for those among them who reject faith a grievous punishment.’

3. **Third Revelation (Surah Al Imran, Verses 130-2)** states that, ‘O believers, take not doubled and redoubled interest, and fear God so that you may prosper. Fear the fire which has been prepared for those who reject faith, and obey God and the Prophet so that you may receive mercy.’

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4. **Fourth Revelation (Surah al-Baqarah, verses 275-81)** states that,

‘Those who benefit from interest shall be raised like those who have been driven to madness by the touch of the Devil, this is because they say. Trade is like interest while God has permitted trade and forbidden interest. Hence, those who have received the admonition from their Lord and desist may have what has already passed, their case being entrusted to God, but those who revert shall be the inhabitants of the fire and abide therein for ever (275). God deprives interest of all blessing but blesses charity; He loves not the ungrateful sinner (276). These, who believe, perform good deeds, establish prayer and pay the Zakat, their reward is with their Lord; neither should they have any fear, nor shall they grieve (277). O believers, fear God, and give up the interest that remains outstanding if you are believers (278). If you do not do so, then be sure of being at war with God and His Messenger. But, if you repent, you can have your principal. Neither should you commit injustice nor should you be subjected to it. (279). If the debtor is in difficulty, let him have respite until it is easier, but if you forego out of charity, it is better for you if you realize (280). And fear the Day when you shall be returned to the Lord and every soul shall be paid in full what it has earned and no one shall be wronged (281)’.

2.1.2.2. Riba in the Hadith².

A. General

1. From Jabir: The Prophet, may peace be upon him, cursed the receiver and the payer of interest, the one who records it and the two witnesses to the transaction and said, ‘They are all alike in guilt’ (Muslim, Kitab al-Musaqat, Bab la‘ni akili al-riba wamu kilihi; also in Trimidhi and Musnad Ahmad)(Safvi, 2017).

2. From Jabir ibn ‘Abdallah: It mentions ‘The Prophet, Peace Be Upon Him (PBUH), addressed the people and said, ‘All of the riba of Jahiliyyah is annulled. The first riba that I annul is our riba, that accruing to Abbas ibn Abd al-Muttalib [The Prophet’s uncle]; it is being cancelled completely. (Kitab al-Hajj, Bab Hajjati al-Nabi, may peace be on him; also in Musnad Ahmad).

3. From ‘Abdallah ibn Hanzalah: The Prophet, peace be upon him, said ‘A Dirham of riba which a man receives knowingly is worse than committing adultery thirty-six times.’ (Mishkat al- Masabih, Kitab al-Buyu Bab al-riba, on the authority of Ahmed and Daraqutni). Bayhaqi has also reported the above hadith in Shu‘ab al-iman with the addition that, ‘Hell befits him whose flesh has been nourished by the unlawful’.

² A collection of traditions containing sayings of the prophet Muhammad (PBUH) which, with accounts of his daily practice (the Sunna), constitute the major source of guidance for Muslims apart from the Koran.

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B. Riba al-Nasi'ah

1. From Usamah ibn Zayd: The Prophet (PBUH); said, 'There is no riba except in nasi'ah [Waiting].' (Bukhari, Kitab al-Buyu, Bab Bay ai-dinari bi aldinar nasa'an). 'There is no riba in hand to hand [spot] transactions.' (Kitab al-Musaqat)

2. From Ibn Mas'ud: The Prophet (PBUH); said, 'Even when interest is much, it is bound to end up into paltriness'. (Ibn Majah Kitab Al Tijarat)

3. From Anas ibn Malik: The Prophet (PBUH); said, 'When one of you grants a loan and the borrower offers him a dish, he should not accept it; and if the borrower offers a ride on an animal, he should not ride, unless the two of them have been previously accustomed to exchanging such favours mutually'. (Sunan al - Bayhaqi, Kitab al-Buyu).

C. Riba al-Fadl.

1. From 'Umar ibn al-Khattab: The last verse to be revealed was on riba and the Prophet, peace be upon him, was taken without explaining it to us; so give up not only riba but also ribah [Whatever raises doubts in the mind about its rightfulness]. (Ibn Majah)

2. From Abu Sa'id al-Khudri: The Prophet, peace be upon him, said, 'Do not sell gold for gold except when it is like for like and do not increase one over the other; do not sell silver for silver except when it is like for like and do not increase one over the other; and do not sell what is away from among these for what is ready. (Bukhari, Kitab al-Buyu, Tirmidhi, Nasa'I and Musnad Ahmad).

3. From 'Ubada ibn al-Samit: The Prophet, peace be upon him, said, 'Gold for gold, silver for silver, wheat for wheat, barley for barley, dates for dates, and salt for salt – like for like, equal for equal, and hand-to-hand; if the commodities differ, then you may sell as you, wish, provided that the exchange is hand-to-hand'. (Kitab al-Musaqat also in Tirmidhi).

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2.1.2.3. Riba in Fiqh³ (Jurisprudence)

1. The Four Schools

Abd al-Rahman al-Jaziri's al-Fiqh ala al-Mad-hahib alarba'ah, is a compendium on the juristic opinions of the four predominant schools of Muslim jurisprudence. It is held in high esteem and considered to be an authority on the subject. Given below are some relevant excerpts from this book on the subject of riba. Definition and classification of Riba is one of those unsound (fasid) transactions which have been severely prohibited (nahyan mughallazan). It literally means increase. However, in Fiqh terminology, Riba means an increase in one of two homogeneous equivalents being accompanied by a return. It is classified into two categories.

a. The first category, riba alnasi'ah where the specified increase is in return for postponement of, or waiting for, the payment; for example, buying an irdab (a specific measure) of wheat in winter against an irdab and a half of wheat to be paid in summer. As the half irdab which has been added to the price was not accompanied by an equivalent value in the commodity sold and was merely in return for the waiting, it is called riba al-nasi'ah.

b. The second category is riba al-fadl which means that the increase mentioned is irrespective of the postponement and is not offset by something in return. This happens when an irdab of wheat is exchanged hand to hand for an irdab and a kilah (another measure) of its own counterpart, the buyer and the seller both taking reciprocal possession; or when ten carats of gold produce are exchanged for twelve carats of similar gold produce.

2.2. The difference between Islamic Economics and Conventional Economics

Every social system has its own economic system. Islam being a comprehensive and distinct social system; possesses a corresponding economic system. Islam is a religion which transcends the ritualistic practices and influences the daily life of a person, it is thus, a way of life for all times and places and hence its system should be flexible. When we speak of economic systems, the textbooks and economists all speak of Western economic systems like the capitalism, socialism etc. because the contemporary economics evolved in the West. The backwardness of Muslim communities since the 16th or 17th centuries led to two things. Firstly, it led to a lack of proper attention to Islamic systems and values and secondly, lack of dynamic development of economic thought in conformity with Islamic principles. Basically,

³ Shariah is the whole divine law and values as given by Allah. Fiqh is the laws extracted by Muslim jurists from the sources of Islamic law. Fiqh contains human involvement which is required as juristic interpretation comes in.

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the Islamic society was stagnant and there was no revival on the lines of reformation and renaissance movements which changed the Western thinking and ushered in radical change in the Western society. With the present revival in Muslim countries and the awareness of the wealth of knowledge in Islam; there seems to be an increasing interest in the studies of Islamic economics.

2.2.1. Definition of the Economic System

The economic system is part and parcel of the social system. It cannot be regarded as a separate entity. The main factors that affect the economic system in any country are:

- a. The historical and ideological background.
- b. The size and geographical location.
- c. The level of development.
- d. The degree of openness.
- e. The political system.

The success of the system will depend on its consistency with all aspects of life. What is the definition of an economic system? Joseph Schumpeter says, 'By a system of political economy I mean an exposition of a comprehensive set of economic policies that its author advocates on the strength of certain unifying (normative) principles such as the principle of economic liberalism, of socialism, and so on'. On the basis of this definition, we can say that the basic organizations or institutions which distinguish one economic system from the other relate to three basic areas. These are, the types of ownership, motivation and decision making process. The role of the government in the economic life is also one of the elements which differentiate the various economic systems. Finally, on a microeconomic level, the economic system should have a say in the four classifications of consumption, production, exchange and distribution. As far as ownership is concerned, three forms can be identified. These are private, public and mixed ownership. The motivation of the various agents in the society could be private profit or public good and welfare. Two main forms of decision making processes could be cited; market mechanism and planning policies. The role of the government in economic life can be either minimal or overwhelming. The organization of the four compartments of microeconomics will differ depending on the type of choice between various institutions cited above. One can make several combinations of the various elements in these institutions.

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2.2.1.1. The Islamic Economic System.

Now, let us see the main elements of an Islamic economic system in the light of the adopted definition.

a. Ownership

Muslim scholars have dealt with the question of ownership in a detailed and comprehensive manner. There is a consensus that it plays a social function. This is true of everything in Islam since all matters in the final analysis pertain to God Almighty. In determining the forms of ownership, Islam recognizes private ownership and preserves it. The Qur'an states "To men is allocated what they earn, and to women what they earn" (4:32). The Prophet (pbuh) said, "A Muslim is not allowed to transgress on another Muslim his life, honor and wealth". Islam may allow some public ownership of the means of production as far as private ownership serves the society better. However, some conditions and restrictions on private property are imposed. The owner should always try to invest his wealth in order to develop the society, and not keep it idle for it will be reduced through the payment of Zakah. The owner should spend in the way of God which will help achieve social solidarity. The use of wealth should not harm other individuals or the society at large. The sources of wealth should be Halal. It should not be realized from Riba, cheating, or monopoly. In the latter cases it could be confiscated for the benefit of the treasury (Bayt al Mal). Wealth should not be used to corrupt the society or to exercise political power.

It could be stated that Islam imposes the general principle of Wasat (balance) when it states in the Quran, "Thus have we made of you an Ummah justly balanced" (2:143). Consequently, ownership in an Islamic economic system is mixed. Both forms of ownership, private and public are allowed.

b. Motivation

Islam, as a way of life, gives due importance for both lives i.e. this world and the hereafter. It does not allow the individual to consider himself the centre of all his activities. The individual in an Islamic society should give due consideration to his relations, towards God Almighty, family, society as well as to himself. This is illustrated by a verse in Qur'an, "But seek, with the (wealth) which God has bestowed on thee, the home of the Hereafter, nor forget thy portion in this World" (28:77). This motivation would give enough incentive for man to work and develop his society, at the same time would save the society from the evils of excessive concentration on the selfish profit motive alone.

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c. Decision making process

Market forces as the sole mechanism for decision making is consistent with private ownership. This is also true of planning in the case of public ownership. Since, Islam allows both forms of ownership, it is only logical to find both methods of decision making in it. The Shura (consultation) principle governs public issues. In case a decision is required about a debatable issue, consultation would rule. The general principle, however, is that economic decisions should be taken in the market place. This stems from the fact that in general administrative pricing (Tasir) is not allowed. The evils which might result from the imperfections of the market would also be minimized through the observance of Islamic values such as forbidding cheating, illegality of excessive rates of profits, moderate consumption patterns even when consumers have the ability to pay. On the other hand, the Islamic State should be concerned with the economic welfare of the generations, the present and the future. Coupled with the existence of some public enterprises a sort of planning should be adopted. With the existence of mixed ownership, indicative planning as it is known should be applied.

d. The role of the state

In Islam the role of the State is neither the guarding state as in capitalism nor is it totalitarian as in socialism. The state in an Islamic economic system has the role of guidance and supervision. It has to create a congenial atmosphere for the progress of the society. Through Zakah and other fiscal tools it has to assure a better distribution of income. The Public sector is allowed to exist, though it should not embrace all the activities in the society. The Government should intervene to strike a balance between private and public interests whenever a conflict arises. This need not be through producing goods by Government; other forms ought to be more efficient. Justice as a general tenet of Islam should be guiding principle for all government activities.

e. The organization of economic activity

The organization of production and exchange should be competitive. Monopoly is generally forbidden.

2.2.1.2. The Conventional Economics

Conventional economics has set before itself two different sets of goals. One of these is what may be termed positive, and relates to the realization of 'efficiency' and 'equity' in the

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allocation and distribution of scarce resources. The other is what may be called normative and is expressed in terms of the universally-desired socioeconomic goals of need-fulfilment, full employment, optimum rate of economic growth, equitable distribution of income and wealth, economic stability, and ecological balance all of which are generally considered indispensable for actualizing human well-being. The use of scarce resources in a way that both the positive and the normative goals are realized brings into focus the need for three indispensable mechanisms: filtering, motivation and socio-economic restructuring.

Firstly, the unlimited claims on resources need to be passed through a filter in such a way that not only a balance is attained between supply and demand but also all those claims are eliminated that are in conflict with goal realization. Secondly, if coercion is ruled out, then such filtering needs to be brought about by motivating all individuals sufficiently to put in their best performance and to abstain from the use of resources in a way that frustrates goal realization. Whether or not conventional economics has been able to realize its positive goals is not possible to say because of the difficulty of defining and measuring both efficiency and equity in a dynamic economy. However, it is generally agreed that even the rich industrial countries have been unable to realize their normative goals in spite of substantial resources at their disposal.

2.3. The Distributive justice and public finance in Islam.

Distributive justice has always been extremely important in all human societies and a lot of social problems and strife has taken place throughout history because of distributive injustice. Islam being a religion; provides numerous goals and means for dealing with this thorny and controversial issue of distributive justice. To begin with a clear distinction has to be made between two concepts of distribution which economists talk about. One is called the functional distribution of income. By this is meant a distribution of income according to the productive agent who receives the income. In this scheme, the division of income is between rent, wages, profits etc. However, the functional distribution of income is not the only theme. The focus here is on the personal distribution of income. In the personal distribution of income, one is looking at how income is distributed among individuals in a society, regardless of how any individual receives his share of income. Moreover, in discussing personal income, one is referring directly to the welfare of individuals.

A person is poor when his income is very low, regardless of the fact, whether this low income is in the form of profits, wages or rent. If his income is high, by the same token, regardless of the type of income, he is said to be rich. So, the personal distribution of income

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has a direct connection with the economic welfare of the individual. Another analytical distinction between distribution and redistribution is as follows: The allocation of income that takes place through mutually agreed transactions among individuals in the market is referred to as distribution and when society uses extra market or other non-market processes to modify that particular distribution it is called redistribution.

2.3.1. Major goals of distributive justice in Islam

Justice is a complex phenomenon and is subject to various interpretations. It may not be useful here to discuss the concept of justice in its abstract form. Hence, in order to focus the discussion, it would be better to specify the particular aspects of justice being discussed. So, let us directly consider Shariah's stand on distribution. The major Islamic goals of distributive justice may be described as follows:

(i) Guarantee of fulfillment of basic needs for all

The guarantee of fulfillment of basic needs of all people in society is a fundamental Islamic objective of distribution and redistribution. It is supported by over whelming rules explicitly stated in the texts in Qur'an and Hadith and there is no doubt as to its importance and primacy in the Islamic concept of distributive justice.

(ii) Reduction of inequalities in income and wealth

The second goal is the reduction of inequality in income and wealth. This goal, is also stated explicit in the Qur'an. Many of the Islamic rules of distribution and redistribution clearly aim to achieve the objective of reducing the inequalities in income and wealth.

(iii) Purification of the donor's inner self and his wealth

The third rule for redistribution is the purification of the donor's inner self and The purification of his wealth. This is also explicitly stated in the Qur'an and in Hadith.

2.3.2. Islamic schemes for distribution and redistribution

Islam uses many tools and schemes for redistribution. These are briefly surveyed below and the analysis also focuses on how Islam deals with the incentive effect of redistribution.

1. Prohibition of interest and promotion of profit sharing

These may be considered as measures operating through the market process, thus, they can be classified as distributive schemes. Let us examine the case of a loan. A

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commercial bank has two applications for financing - one from a poor man and the other from a rich person. Let us assume that the two projects present their prospects of profit and loss as similar. If the bank is financing on the basis of interest-based system, it is mainly concerned about getting back its principle plus interest (Riba) as stipulated in the contract. Now what guarantee is there that the principal will come back plus the stipulated Riba? In the traditional banking setup confidence is generated by the wealth of the borrowers. If the borrower is wealthy, he has a number of other commercial assets such as land, buildings and other businesses. The bank may assume that if he fails in this particular project, it may claim part of his wealth and get back its loan and the interest. So, the existence of prior wealth of the applicant is a guarantee for the financier that he will get back the principal plus the interest. The other person, who has an equally good project but does not have sufficient wealth, has almost no chance of getting financed. In fact, this is not a hypothetical possibility. Several studies of distribution of financing in industrial countries have shown that this effect is magnified many times over.

This process usually goes on for generation after generation. The very nature of loan financing on the basis of interest allocates more resources to the rich and deprives the poor of finance. Compare this with financing based on profit sharing. In profit sharing the financier is not sure that the principal and his share of profit will materialize unless the project is successful. He cannot go and take the property of the receiver if the project fails. So, his attention is devoted to scrutinizing the project itself. If it succeeds, he gains, if it does not, he loses. So, the banker in the Islamic system has no personal interest to seek the rich particularly and give them money. He will seek the best project. This is not only more efficient for society as a whole but also more just because the distribution of honest and good projects is not confined to the rich alone. When the financing is done on the basis of profit sharing the poor have a much better chance of getting some amount of financing as compared to the interest based system.

2. Prohibition of monopoly

Monopolies have many forms; some are natural, some contrived and some are administratively created by society. Islam clearly prohibits monopoly except in those cases where monopoly has to be tolerated because of peculiarities in the processes of production. Shariah and Fuqaha have clearly stated that if monopoly for some reason is inevitable or unavoidable (by giving the examples and monopolies existing in their own times) the government must intervene and control the price of the product. The elimination of monopoly

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helps considerably in eliminating a reason for the creation of disparities of income and wealth.

3. Measures for distributing natural wealth

This feature is unique in Islam specifically when compared with all known systems at the time when Islam was revealed. Islam has specific rules regarding the distribution of natural wealth among the population; some of them are mentioned here;

(a) Partnership of all citizens in certain kinds of wealth

There is an authentic Hadith of Prophet (pbuh), the Muslims are partners in Three things, in water, pastures and fire. Other types of natural wealth could be covered by Qiyas (analogy) under the same Hadith. Imam Shafei has a long list of items such as salt, sulphur, naphtha, etc. falling under the same category. Natural wealth has two characteristics in common. The first is that natural resources should be easily accessible to all people and second they should not have to pay excessive costs for reaching them. There are also some other rules and conditions with the same implications. In brief, there are certain types of natural resources that Islam stipulates to be freely accessible to all citizens of the country. Imam Sharakhshi the well-known Hanafi jurist says that non-Muslims in an Islamic society also have similar access to these natural resources on an equal footing with Muslims (IIBF, 2022). So there are some types of wealth in which all people are partners or they have free access to it. Why and how does this affect distribution of income and wealth? Suppose, elementary education is provided free to all citizens, it means that all people can have access to free elementary education regardless of their wealth. Consequently, the real value of education becomes equal or nearly so among all people.

(b) Prohibition of private preserves (Enclosures)

Another rule of Shariah leads to the same result. Al-Hima means keeping people away from land which was earlier treated as Mubah (useable by all) so as to restrict to the beneficiary all outward benefits which do not require significant efforts or expenditure on his part.

2.4. Various financing types and products and services offered by Shariah banking system

When professional economists took over the task of developing Islamic economics as a social science, it was a welcome transition from religious scholars to professionals. The earlier contributions by religious scholars were mostly theological, explaining various tenets

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of Islam. The professional economists started reflecting on various technical dimensions of the subject which was yet at an embryonic stage. Methodology of Islamic economics was one of the subjects they took up for discussion and development.

We experience today that uncontrolled capitalism has plunged the global economy into an unprecedented crisis. This calls for a need to eradicating huge bubbles of fiat money (fiat money, in a broad sense includes, all kinds of money that are made legal tender by a government decree or fiat. The term is, however, usually reserved for legal-tender paper money or coins that have face values far exceeding their commodity values and are not redeemable in gold or silver) and assets brought in by capitalism and build up a real and stable economy. In the wake of crisis, world has slowly started shifting to this alternate financing model which offers a wide range of complex financial tools viz., Mudaraba, Murabaha, Musharaka, Istisna, Musaqat and Ijarah. Though, Islamic financing has been creating waves in the global economy, it is yet to get a go ahead in India. One of the reasons for this is its non-consonance with the prevailing provisions of Banking Regulations Act.

Islamic banking is a financial system that is consistent with the principles of Shariah law. Shariah prohibits the fixed or floating payment or acceptance of specific interest or fees (known as riba, or usury) for loans of money. The Vatican has put forward the idea that, ‘the principles of Islamic finance may represent a possible cure for ailing markets’. The international market for Islamic finance has grown between 10 to 15 percent annually in recent years. At this rate, it is the world’s fastest growing financial sector and is becoming an increasingly important component of the international financial system. Islamic banking is the most popular form of financial institution and it is estimated to be into several hundred billion dollars. There are different models of Islamic banking, where in the Islamic banking is a private institution with a traditional conventional economy. A nationalized Islamic banking and third is the existence of both the Islamic and conventional banking system running parallel.

2.4.1. Basic Tenets of Islamic banking are as follows

The basic tenets of Islamic banking and finance can be put down as under:

- a. Prohibition of interest-based (riba) transactions.
- b. Ban on speculation and excessive risk taking (gharar).
- c. Islamic tax system (Zakat).
- d. Discouragement of the production of goods and services which contradict the value pattern of Islam (haram).

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2.4.2. Modes of deposit mobilization by Islamic banks

We have seen above the Advances (Loan) products offered by the Islamic Banks. As discussed in the Chapter 1, a bank needs to have deposits in order to offer loans. We already have some general idea of deposit products which are offered by banks. Islamic banks or Shariah banks also offer similar deposit products to their customers. The study of deposit products and how these differ from those in regular banks will further help us to understand the Shariah banking system as well as how it is more ethical in nature.

1. Current accounts

Current accounts are based on the principle of Al-wadiah, where the depositors are guaranteed repayment of their funds. At the same time, the depositor does not receive remuneration for depositing funds in a current account because the guaranteed funds will not be used for Profit & Loss Sharing (PLS) ventures. Rather, the funds accumulated in these accounts can only be used to balance the liquidity needs of the bank and for short-term transactions on the bank's responsibility.

2. Savings accounts

Savings accounts also operate under the Al-wadiah principle. Savings accounts differ from current deposits in that they earn the depositors income: depending upon financial results, the Islamic bank may decide to pay a premium, riba at its discretion to the account holders.

3. Investment accounts

An investment account operates under the mudaraba-al-mutlaqa principle, in which the mudarib must have absolute freedom in the management of the investment of the subscribed capital. The conditions of this account differ from those of the savings accounts by virtue of: a) higher fixed minimum amount, b) longer duration of deposits and c) the depositor may lose some of or all his funds in the event of the bank making losses, i.e. the principal or the rate of return on the deposits is not guaranteed. The only contractual agreement between investment depositors and banks is the proportion according to which profits or losses are to be distributed between the parties of the deposit contract. The pooled amount is then invested in a business acceptable to Shariah.

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4. Joint/General investment account

The most prevalent practice among Islamic banks is to establish some kind of investment pool in lieu of fixed term deposits. The investment pool takes the form of a general investment account in which investment deposits of different maturities are put together. These are not tied to any specific investment project but are utilized in different financing operations of the bank. Profits are calculated and distributed at the end of the accounting period which is three months, six months or one year. Another variation of the investment pool is the establishment of a Joint Investment Account which is defined by the Jordan Islamic Bank as cash deposits received by the bank from persons desiring to participate with the bank in multilateral and continuous investment and financing operations whereby such deposits will receive a certain percentage of annual profits realized in accordance with the conditions of the account under which they are entered.

5. Limited Period Investment Deposits

These deposits are operated by the Bahrain Islamic Bank and the Kuwait Finance House. Investment deposits under this scheme are accepted for a specified period which is mutually determined by the depositor and the bank. The contract terminates at the end of the specified period but profits are calculated and distributed at the end of the financial year.

6. Unlimited Period Investment Deposits

These investment deposits differ from limited period deposits in that the Period is not specified. Deposits are automatically renewable unless a notice of three months is given to terminate the contract. No withdrawals or further deposits are permitted in this kind of contract but customers are allowed to open more than one account. The profits are calculated and distributed at the end of the financial year.

7. Specified Investment Deposits

Some Islamic banks have developed an investment deposit scheme with specific authorization to invest in a particular project or trade. In this case, only the profits of this particular project are distributed between the bank and its customers according to mutually agreed terms and conditions.

As noticed above, the Shariah banks also receive deposits from their depositors/customers and in-turn invests the amount in order to earn profit. Islamic investors may only invest in activities that are in strict compliance with Shariah precepts. Private

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equity funds wishing to be Islamic compliant cannot invest in the following industries: the manufacture, packaging or distribution of alcohol, tobacco or pork products; entertainment; conventional financial services; the manufacture and sale of weapons; or other industries not compatible with Shariah as interpreted by the Shariah board of a fund. In addition, indirect investments in any of these industries are also prohibited. For example, private equity funds wishing to market to Islamic investors cannot invest in real estate opportunities which lease space to restaurants serving alcohol or pork products or lease offices occupied by conventional banking and financial institutions or insurance companies. Where these situations arise, a mixture of legal segregation mechanisms as well as purification processes have been utilized to ensure Shariah compliance of the underlying property investments. Unless a financial institution is prohibited for regulatory reasons from doing so, it is well established that almost any financial institution is permitted to offer Islamic investment products. A non-Islamic bank or a non-Muslim can engage in trading or investing in a Shariah compliant manner. A conventional financial institution in London or New York is permitted, therefore, to promote an Islamic private equity fund that caters to the needs of its Muslim investors. In many instances, this does not require the formation of an independent subsidiary. Typically, a separate department within an institution can develop and offer Shariah compliant products. Some jurisdictions, however, may require that Islamic banking licenses be independent from conventional licenses with the obvious result that the banking industry in such a jurisdiction provides for two parallel systems namely Islamic and conventional. A sponsor of the venture capital fund can act as a Mudareb under a Mudaraba arrangement, a Wakeel under a Wakala (agency) arrangement or an investment manager pursuant to an investment management agreement. In other words, it is not a requirement of Islamic investment that the investment manager enter into a specific form of investment management agreement for the purposes of an Islamic private equity fund or any other fund for that matter. The investment management agreement must, however, provide for detailed investment guidelines which are derived from Shariah over and above the fund-specific investment restrictions.

2.5. Contribution of small financing method in the economic growth of few economies

In this segment I shall emphasize on the contribution of Islamic banking in the development of two economies in South Asia namely Indonesia and Bangladesh. The similarity between them and India is that they are agrarian economies, i.e. the major sector of economy is agriculture, both in the share of GDP and the percentage of population employed

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in it. The main difference is that while India is a secular republic the other two are Islamic majority nations. Still, I shall point out how Islamic banking has played a major role in stabilizing and the growth of the priority sector in these two countries.

2.5.1. Indonesia

Agricultural production may also be a source of foreign exchange. However, most of the poor people in the country work in the agricultural sector. Although the farming sector is a major contributor to the national economy, unfortunately, many farmers still live below the poverty line (Utama et al., 2019). Regarding the banking industry in Indonesia, it is still dominated by corporate financing and consumer financing. The bank finance policy also does not support the agricultural sector, which is one of the main pillars of the Indonesian economy (Utama et al., 2019). At the end of 2016, the total agricultural credit provided to farmers' amounts to just 14.85% of the total bank loans. Despite the lack of capital, farming and agriculture are still reluctant to involve banks in meeting financing needs. Farmers prefer informal financing, such as landlords and families, rather than financing their agricultural plans through banks. Such funding alternatives are driven by farmers' way to eliminate the complicated bureaucracies of banks and their high-interest rates (Meutia et al., 2017). One of the reasons why banks have not provided intensive financing to agricultural entrepreneurs is an agricultural risk. The bad weather causes crop prices to fluctuate, so farmers often pay late or even refuse to pay the bank's installment against debt. The 3.32 non-performing loan from the agricultural industry is higher than the 3.18 NPL of the banking sector (Meutia et al., 2017).

According to (Young-kon, n.d.), the natural resources, the vast and fertile lands are not sufficient to make farmers successful. They still need seeds, fertilizers, pesticides, and agricultural machinery as inputs for growing agricultural produce. However, Farmers do not have strong capital until the harvest time comes, to fund all the farming project activities. The yield of last year's harvest is one of the key sources of farmer's capital. Farmers usually have to sell their crops as soon as possible to earn cash, so crops are most often sold at a low price. Moreover, farmers do not earn sufficient money to support their households or to increase their agricultural production (Ahmed et al., 2012).

2.5.1.1. Problems faced by the farmers in Indonesia

i. Farmers had insufficient funds: Independent small-scale farmers managed about 30% of the farmland in Indonesia (2018, data) which is a significant number. These farmers faced

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economic challenges, such as low productivity and crop quality, as well as environmental and social challenges, such as deforestation, fires and haze, and social conflict. One of the main reasons for these challenges was due to lack of funds.

ii. Problem of working capital due to limited access to banks: Indonesian farmers were largely excluded from formal financial services which was evident as only 5% of lending went to a sector that contributed 13.6% to the GDP, and most of this went to larger commercial plantations. Wherever bank credit was available it generally required collateral and this is a common problem faced by almost 90% of Indonesian smallholders who do not have formal title to their land. Limited access to resources and credit is a key hindrance for smallholders in Indonesia to improve their productivity and net income. Further complicating rural credit was the small farm size (around one hectare on average), and the lack of strong farmer groups that can help channel fertilizers, credit, and market produce. Hasanah (2003) points out that the non-utilization of waqf assets is due to the lack of skill of the Mutawalli. Prihatna (2005) agrees that the failure of waqf in solving many problems in Indonesia is not because of the reduction in, or lack of, waqf assets; but rather due to the improper management and unskilled Mutawalli (Damkar et al., 2021).

Amidst all these, Shariah banking grew in Indonesia, but the development of Islamic banking is currently induced to lead to the conventional financial system (N. Zaman & Mehmet Asutay, 2017) as well as in the social aspects resulting from the transformation to commercial banking (Mehmet, 2012). One of the arguments over the criticisms above, according to Asutay (2012), is that the majority of financing Islamic banking is a murabahah scheme, with a mark-up scheme that is debt-based like a conventional bank, while other contracts such as mudarabah, musharaka and qard al-hassan which are the main characteristics (Islamic banks are often referred to as banks with profit-sharing principles to assert differences with conventional banks) of Islamic banking portions are still very small. In the case of Indonesia, in March 2017, the proportion of financing with murabahah scheme still dominates 57 percent of total financing. The Islamic finance to agriculture sector was a meager 6% (Source: Statistic of Islamic Banking, 2017). One reason being that it was a high risk sector but the statistics show that the NPA percentage is very low (3.6%) which was considerably better than two main sectors of banking, i.e. commerce and industry during the same period.

Islamic banking, as part of the Islamic economic system, has the responsibility towards the welfare of society. Therefore, the presence of Islamic banking should be felt at

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all levels of the society, especially the poor because Islam is basically in favour of the poor. The agricultural sector which is the backbone of the national economy but still a hotbed of poverty has not really been touched by Islamic banking. This is evident from the size of the proportion of finances allotted to the agricultural sector which until now is no more than 10 percent of the total financing issued, in spite of this sector being the second largest contributor of GDP and the largest absorber of labour in Indonesia. However, poverty is still a classic problem in the agricultural sector. Islamic banking with all its potential is expected to engage more in this sector, because the contracts used are very applicable to agriculture. Agricultural financing performance as seen from Non Performance Financing shows that if this sector is managed very well then the risks that are feared can be avoided. The data shows that the performance of financing the agricultural sector is better than the two sectors that always become the mainstay of Islamic financing. To that end, the government as the holder of the policy authority should encourage the banking sector to pay more attention to the agricultural sector. In addition, the process of financing should be done in a partnership relationship between banks and the farmers. In this case, the banks can assist the farmers who are financed. In addition, Islamic banks can also apply the financing model of Ba'i As Salam as an alternative solution that equally benefits the farmers and the Islamic banking (Utama et al., 2019). But, it's a gradual beginning and I am hopeful that the Islamic banking will lead in agriculture and MSE finance in Indonesia in the coming days.

2.5.2. Islamic finance in Bangladesh

The economic growth and stability in Bangladesh has been credited largely to Muhammad Yunus, (Yunus, 2007), who is regarded as the 'Father of micro-economy'. Hence we see that while comparatively larger economies like Pakistan, and similar sized economies like Sri-Lanka have collapsed, Bangladesh remains stable and growing. This is due to the penetration of 'Grameen banking' or Micro-finance to the grassroots of the country. It is estimated that Grameen bank provides financial loan to about 7.0 million people, 97% of whom are women, in 73000 villages across Bangladesh. The Grameen Bank's (GB) 'Empowering the Poor' model has achieved global recognition as a tool for alleviating poverty (Besley & Coate., 1995). GB is considered as an exceptional success story in Bangladesh, given that in other developing countries financial institutions in rural areas really struggle to achieve the goals set by the government and donor agencies (Jain, 1996). By developing this model with the formation of the GB in 1983, Professor Muhammad Yunus showed that microcredit lenders could achieve higher loan recovery rates and returns, even in

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the absence of collateral. Conventionally, this market had been considered very risky and non-bankable by the formal financial sector, but the GB's microcredit model changed the whole perception of risk in this large segment of the population (Suzuki et al., 2013).

The average level of NPL of the Islamic banks is lower than that of other private banks and state-owned banks. Most importantly, in recent years, for instance during 2009–2010, the level of NPL of the Islamic banks has been lower than foreign banks. On the other hand, it is also evident that Islamic banks have consistently enjoyed a steady growth in return on assets (ROA) over the years. Although their ROA was lower than the foreign banks, it was still higher than that of state-owned banks and all private banks, except for the year 2007. The lower level of NPL in the Islamic banking sector of Bangladesh has been explained in four different ways. First, in the view of Mohsin S. Khan, the Islamic banking system may well turn out to be better suited than the conventional interest-based commercial banking system to adjust to the kind of shocks that can lead to banking crises (Ayub, 2007). This view implies that the Islamic banks can more quickly diversify or socialize the underlying credit risk like investment banks or securities brokers in the 'direct finance' route of financing. Second, in non-participatory financing, particularly under the Murabaha system, Islamic finance theoretically poses a lower level of risk to the participating institutions than conventional financing, as financial losses are borne either in whole or in part by the customer, although commercial reality does diverge to some extent from the theory (Siddiqui, 1983). Third, the large proportion of risk-averse depositors investing in Islamic banks provides them with an incentive to select low-risk assets for their portfolios which further contributes to the lower level of NPL. Fourth, Islamic banks necessarily have to be very selective in choosing their borrowers under the prohibition of *gharar*, which may also result in a lower NPL.

2.5.3. Difference between Grameen Bank and Islamic bank

There is a significant difference between these two systems when it comes to the target group and the client base. GB microcredit is targeted at the marginalized poor of rural areas of Bangladesh, its members and borrowers lie at the bottom of the economic ladder in society. More importantly, 98% of GB members are rural women. It is a kind of organization where higher levels of income, wealth, and land ownership become disqualifications for borrowing and membership. Also, the GB offers microcredit on the basis of group collateral, with no assets underwriting the lending. On the other hand, the Islamic banking operations of most of the banks are still confined to urban or semi-urban areas and their target groups are

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different from those of the GB. Yet, the portfolio of lending of Islamic banking is dominated by forms of financing like Murabaha and Ijara, which are backed by assets. So, from an institutional viewpoint, Islamic banking and the GB are essentially not competitors. Rather, GB borrowers, after moving from below to above the poverty line, may eventually become clients of Islamic banks. The involvement of one of the Islamic banks with the development of small entrepreneurs in Bangladesh by adopting the operating system of the GB in accordance with the framework of Islamic Shari'ah, as reported by (Hamid, 2005), gives an indication of the possible complementarities of the two systems of banking.

2.5.4. Grameen Banks compliment Islamic Banks in Bangladesh

Both Islamic banking and the GB model of microcredit have been successful in creating their own business domains in Bangladesh. By analyzing and comparing the incentive and sanction methods in both the systems, I have attempted to provide theoretical explanation of the rationale behind the two mechanisms from a philosophical standpoint. At present, they are not substitutes for each other. But the GB may have a long-term influence on Islamic banking if and when some former borrowers from the GB become clients of Islamic banks after rising up the poverty ladder. In the economic context of Bangladesh, we find that the Islamic banks are engaged in providing 'non-participatory' finance, mainly to Muslim traders and merchants in urban areas. Due to the scarcity of 'risk' fund in their liability structure and the opportunity to capture definite pledged returns from non-participatory financing, the current asset portfolio management by the Islamic banks makes sense. However, Bangladeshi institutions in general, and those of the Muslim community in particular, have generally failed in channelling funds into new ventures and large-scale projects, which require a diversification of risk. The pertinent question we ask is how the Islamic banks can develop a diversified base of depositors who can absorb the associated potential loss, in order to encourage the banks to engage more in participatory financing? This is an important challenge not only to the Islamic banks, but also to the wider Bangladeshi economy. On the other hand, the GB is engaged in providing micro-financing mainly to the individuals in rural areas. Capitalizing on the informal social structure coupled with group monitoring, together with donors' contribution of concessional funds, made the GB a success. However, Bangladeshi society, and in particular the rural community, has failed institutionally to incubate further enterprises based on GB microcredit. Since the rationale of the donors' concessional funds lay mainly in rural development, the more entrepreneurial individuals may be less suited to the microcredit business. How can the

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society develop a formal financial sector to further encourage its viable entrepreneurs? This is an important issue to be considered for the future economy of Bangladesh. Also financing to the sector being catered by the GB is the only way ahead for the Islamic banks if they want to become a primary player in national financial system. Here also we find the struggle between mass and class, wherein the Islamic banks seem to have forsaken the later for the former. Hence, I reiterate my point that the liberation philosophy of Marxist economy is needed alongside the Shariah financial system to make it inclusive irrespective of class, religion and other differences.

2.6. Communitarian aspect of the Shariah banking system

Charity includes zakah, sadaqa, awqaf while gifts include hiba and tabarru. Sadaqa, hiba and tabarru have parallels in conventional microfinance, such as, donations or contributions, zakah and awqaf have a special place in the Islamic system and are governed by elaborate fiqhi rules. Zakah is one of the five pillars of Islam and is meant to finance the poorest of the poor. These sections of the society are unlikely to have positive-Net Present Value projects in need of financing and hence, are considered to be ‘unbankable’. Considering the fact that we have a huge segment of such unbankable population, we need to seriously consider the usage of Zakah to help them. Awqaf creates and preserves long-term assets that generate income flows or indirectly help the process of production and creation of wealth. By targeting its benefits towards the poor, awqaf can play an important role in poverty alleviation. Though there has been significant improvement in management of zakah and awqaf in recent years, their role as vehicles of microfinance and poverty alleviation is grossly underestimated. Their growing popularity evidenced through establishment of many a zakah fund and awqaf fund is an indication of their vast potential in Muslim societies. We need to create awareness about these two instruments in all sections of the Indian society so that the benefits and surplus funds can be directed towards the upliftment and empowerment of the marginalized segment of the Indian population.

Similarly, there also needs to be a transparency in the management of these two funds not just in theory but also on the ground zero, so that individual investors can monitor the disbursement of their fund. This will increase the investor confidence and promote transparency and accountability in the organizations that manage these funds. Care must also be taken to note that these funds be distributed equally and for the actual purpose of their origin, irrespective of any differences between the beneficiaries. Hence, although the funds

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will be governed by the laws of ethics provided by the Islamic scriptures, they will be open for investors and beneficiaries of all religions, gender and other differences.

I conclude this segment by stating that I am not introducing a foreign idea of helping the poor and marginalized in Shariah banking, but it is an integral aspect of the Islamic scriptures and needs to be upheld.

2.7. Reflections on the Shariah Banking system

The growth of Islamic finance to become part of mainstream global finance is not driven purely by sacred intentions of fulfilling religious obligations but also a powerful political-economic weapon for control. Over the years, Islamic finance had to undergo transformation in order to become acceptable as part of the global finance community and in the process, the traditional sacred intentions of fulfilling religious obligations and acting as part of the act of worship became perplexed with the secular goals of modernity (Haniffa & Mohammad, 2010). It had to embrace modern ideas and embrace the technological progress to remain relevant and in the race with other secular institutions. Yet, it was also grounded in the Islamic ideals of morality and fairness which set it aside from its peers.

There have also been these recent developments in Shariah banking where we find, genuine sacred intentions by individual Islamic bankers who visualize a banking system that comply with the goals of Shariah. Their limited knowledge and experience of fiqh left them with no option but to consult well known names in fiqh for guidance as well as commitment to abide by the rules of Shariah not only related to the prohibition of interest but also in terms of Shariah compatibility of financial transactions. There also exist another group of neo-liberal Muslim entrepreneurs or Muslim bourgeois who were more interested in enhancing their economic and political reputation under the guise of Islamic solidarity. Such individuals managed to charm and captivate the common minds in accepting their reasoning and practices although at times pushing the boundaries of Shariah. Their motive in interacting with fiqh scholars was to get their endorsement in liberalizing the industry. Their attempt bears fruit with the fatwa in 1989 by the Grand Mufti of Al-Azhar, Sheikh Tantawi, who legitimised interest by allowing for new pragmatism in the interpretation of *riba* as interest (Mallat, 1996). This fatwa provided Islamic bankers more bargaining power to expand globally. Hence, this period marks the start when sacred intentions became mixed with secular goals facilitated by the alliance with highly respected Shariah scholars.

I see a struggle within the Islamic banking system, a struggle between modernity and relevance on one side and orthodoxy and common good on the other. Despite basing its

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philosophy on moral and ethical standards, the lure of increased profits is enough to shake the foundations of any business. In this struggle I see two factors:

i. Need of a legally authorized and scholarly recognized body of individuals with good moral standards to create a framework of standard operating procedures for Islamic Banking in India. This body will also be responsible to oversee the working of Islamic banks and also create and modify its laws and governing principles from time to time as per the needs of the Society, at the same time be true to the ethical standards set by the Holy Quran. This will prevent scrupulous elements from using their capability to influence individual Islamic authorities with questionable reputations to issue 'fatwas' which suit their requirement, while going against the teachings of Islam and the good of the people.

ii. To remain true to its root of public welfare especially the good of the poor, Islamic economics needs the solid backing of the liberation philosophy of Karl Marx. The Marxian philosophy will always provide a perspective of the good of people especially the proletariat or the farmers and the working class. It will thus, prohibit the unscrupulous elements from hijacking the structure of Islamic banking in their greed for profit, as has happened with the commercial banking. However, Islamic banking unlike commercial banking has the ethical foundations of Islamic scriptures and writings which can be used as a check to prevent its degradation. Marxian philosophy of liberation will provide the extra check to keep it true to its objective of the good of all people especially the poor.

This leads us to the next Chapter, to understand Marxist philosophy of liberation and how it can help the Shariah system in remaining true to its moral and ethical foundations.

Chapter Three

The Liberation Philosophy of Karl Marx

3.1. Introduction to Economic Liberation theory of Karl Marx

Karl Marx was a nineteenth century German economic theorist and philosopher. He is best remembered now for his ideas which led to the development of Communism and Socialism. His most famous books are *The Communist Manifesto* and *Das Kapital*. Marxist ideas have been used both explicitly and implicitly by liberation theologians. Gustavo Gutierrez used Marx implicitly while Leonardo Boff and Jose Miranda have explicitly discussed the relationship between Marxism and Christianity. In general, liberation theologians use Marx as a tool for understanding poverty. They do not adopt his ideas wholesale, but borrow concepts and terminology which they find helpful (Influence of Marx., n.d.). Leonardo Boff mentions this in context to Marxism and Liberation philosophy, 'In liberation theology, Marxism is never treated as a subject on its own but always from and in relation to the poor. Placing themselves firmly on the side of the poor, liberation theologians ask Marx: 'What can you tell us about the situation of poverty and ways of overcoming it?' Here Marxists are submitted to the judgment of the poor and their cause, and not the other way around.' Leonardo Boff took pains to stress that liberation theology is not the same as Marxism. Marx's ideas were used because they were perceived to be useful in the Latin American context. Again these ideas were used by philosophers and theologians across the world in context to the liberation philosophy and their own social conditions to form their philosophy. As Leonardo Buff says, 'Therefore, liberation theology used Marxism purely as an instrument. It does not venerate it as it venerates the gospel. And it feels no obligation to account to social scientists for any use it may make - correct or otherwise of Marxist terminology and ideas...To put it in more specific terms, liberation theology freely borrows from Marxism certain 'methodological pointers' that have proved fruitful in understanding the world of the oppressed.'

3.2. The Philosophy of Karl Marx: Dialectical (historical) Materialism

Historical materialism is the idea that economics is the basis of everything. The political structures a society has, its philosophy, even its art are a reflection of the concerns of the economic ruling class. Furthermore, each economic ruling class is destined to be superseded through class struggle. On reflecting over this view I find that it does hold a

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certain amount of truth, although not complete. The political and social scenario in-fact even our arts showed the concerns of the economic elites; it is visible when we compare the Indian society during different decades. The 60's showed a classic clash of ideals with socialism and capitalism, the 70's and 80's was concerned with the widening gap between the rich and the poor, while the 90's with opening of the economy to globalization and the emergence of the urban corporate elite class brought a westernized and modern India to the fore while the rural and poor India was brushed under the carpet.

3.2.1. What is the Historical Materialism?

Marxian philosophy was historical materialist philosophy. Philosophy is a way of explaining life and the world. More precisely, philosophy is an outlook of the fundamental problems of life and the world. A philosopher starts his thinking with the exercise of rationality. He makes a rational investigation of the problems with which he is concerned. In this sense, philosophy is a rational outlook of the fundamental problems of life and the world. A philosopher is a rational and critical thinker and through his way of thinking he formulates his ideas and builds theories about life and the world. In this sense, philosophy is mainly a theoretical activity and a philosopher is concerned with conceptual or theoretical activity. This is the traditional way of defining philosophy.

It was Karl Marx, who broke this tradition of philosophy and provided an alternative definition of philosophy. The function of philosophy, according to him, is not only to explain the world but also to change it. Philosophy is not only confined with theoretical activity, it is also concerned with practical issues and problems of life. Hence philosophy is both a theory and a practice. As a theory it explains the basic concepts, and as a practice it applies these concepts to practical life. Theory and practice, for Marx, are inseparably connected to each other. They are two aspects of the same objective reality. Marx attempted to make a synthesis between theory and practice. That does not mean that Marx rejected theoretical activity as an important aspect of understanding the world. What he wanted to say is that the function of theory is to provide general idea about man's practical activity, to discover the general nature of the world and to play a supportive role in changing the world. However, no theory independently, i.e. apart from practice can play the role in changing the objective world. It can do this job only in close association with practice. Here lies the relation between theory and practice. Marx was the first philosopher who clearly showed this relation and combined theory with practice. I agree that a fair reading of Marx will show that he had brought about an epistemological break in the history of philosophy. In other words, Marx had brought

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about a revolution in human thought, particularly in the history of philosophical thoughts. He had fundamentally changed the way of how we explain the problems of our life and the world. According to Marx, philosophy is not a pure theoretical activity, it is not an abstract thought isolated from concrete social life; rather it is inseparably connected with social reality. Concrete life process of concrete man is the basis of philosophy. That is to say, practical activity of life is the basis of philosophy. In this sense, philosophy is practical, i.e., philosophy not only explains social life but also paves the way of changing it.

3.2.2. Why should we read Marx today?

Marx died one hundred and forty years ago (on 14 March 1883). Since then so much has happened. Marxist regimes and socialist society based on Marxist philosophy have failed. The collapse of Soviet socialism or the fall of the Berlin Wall has often taken to be the fall of Marxism (that is, Marxism as a dead philosophy). If so, then what is the point of studying Marx today? The first and the most important point of reading and understanding Marx's thought is that he was one of a handful of thinkers who have fundamentally changed the way we see the world. Marx formulated his philosophy in *The German Ideology* (Callinicos, 1987) as the materialist conception of history. This can be considered to be a scientific philosophy which provides a practical interpretation of history. Marx will forever be remembered for this powerful tool of explaining the history of human society. That is why we have to cherish the legacy of his philosophy by understanding his scientific thought about the world. Marx derived his materialist philosophy from the 'simple fact of history' that 'mankind must first of all eat, drink, have shelter and clothing, before it can pursue politics, science, art, religion, etc'(Callinicos, 1987). He is a philosopher in the sense that he provided a materialist interpretation of history. He not only made a theoretical investigation of why revolution happens but also participated in several revolutionary activities to create new chapter of human history.

Understanding Marx's thought is essential for all those who seek the self-emancipation of the working class, the poor and marginalized and who wish to do away with the exploitation built into the capitalist system. Unfortunately, understanding Marx is not always as simple as it should be. This is not because his writings are obscure but because his ideas have undergone many distortions not only by his opponents but also a few of his more fanatic followers.

3.2.3. Philosophical Legacy of Marx

Marxism, from its very emergence, has raised enormous controversies which resulted in different trends like Classical Marxism, Western Marxism, Analytical Marxism, Normative Marxism etc. and various sorts of confusions arise from it. Particularly, there remains a controversy as to the question whether Marxism can be called a philosophy because it does not suggest any definite theory, it deals with different aspects of man and society and discovers different theories concerning society, economics, politics, history etc. However, all these theories have their foundation on philosophy. So, to understand Marxism as a whole, first of all, we have to understand its philosophical foundation. A general objection against Marxism is that it emphasizes more on economics rather than on philosophy, and as a consequence it culminates in economic determinism. I think that this sort of objection is due to misreading and misunderstanding of Marx's thought. A unique feature of Marx's philosophy is that he did not start his thought with straightforward philosophical issues like ontology or epistemology or ethics. He started his philosophical thought with the critique of traditional philosophers. So, to get a clear understanding of his philosophy, we need to have a fair reading of his critique of traditional philosophy. Marx's philosophical thought is that philosophers have interpreted the world in various ways however the point of studying philosophy is to change it. From the philosophical point of view, I argue, this is the most significant statement of Marx. The essence of Marxist philosophy is clearly reflected in this thesis, which can be considered to be the ground of his philosophical thought. This thesis, in my opinion, has made him the status of the philosopher of the philosophers. If we analyze this thesis, two important philosophical aspects of it would become evident. On the one hand, it is Marx's critique towards traditional philosophers through which he had been able to break the wall of philosophical traditions. On the other hand, his own philosophical thought is reflected in it, which has established Marxism as a practical or scientific philosophy (philosophy of praxis).

Marx's principal academic field of expertise was in philosophy. He did his Doctoral thesis on Greek atomism entitled as the 'Difference between the Democritean and Epicurean Philosophy of Nature'. In this thesis Marx spoke about the relation of matter to consciousness and it became the main theme of his materialism. As a matter of fact, this can be considered to be his first form of materialism, according to which man is not controlled or determined by any force other than himself, he is directed by his own will, i.e., he is free; God does not create man's fate, man himself is the creator of his own fate. Marx was inspired by Epicurean philosophy of nature that man is not mechanically determined by strict causal necessity, he

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has the power to transcend this causal chain i.e. he has freedom of will. He declared that it was philosophy, not God or religion that could help man to live and to provide him with a practical outlook of life. The function of philosophy according to Marx is to make man aware of his consciousness and to make him conscious about his freedom. However, Marx's first philosophical thought was reflected in his school essay 'On the choice of a profession of a young Man'. In this essay he suggested that young man should work for the cause of humanity, he should choose such a profession which can serve for the whole mankind and dedicate his life for the cause of humanity. This reveals Marx's humanistic philosophy at the early age of his life which later became the basis of his philosophical thought. Marx's early writings contain philosophical issues. But in his later thoughts he focused on political economy and the history of capitalism. It is said that there happens to be an epistemological break between Marx's early writings (mainly philosophical and psychological) and later writings (socio-political and economic) but that is not the case. There is no break observed in Marx's thoughts and his later writings are the continuation of his early works. Marx's early works became the foundation of his later works. His philosophical ideas are the basis of his socio-political and economic thoughts. There can be no doubt that Marx was a philosopher. However, it is more appropriate to describe him as a social, political and economic philosopher as well as a philosopher of social revolution. Marx was a philosopher in the sense that he was a systematic thinker and he applied dialectics as a scientific method to understand man and society and most importantly to try and bring about a change in the society. He thus formulated a general outlook about human society. Marx was not a philosopher in the traditional sense, he was not concerned with the nature of reality, he was not a system builder rather he had broken this tradition of philosophy. Marx's socio-economic and political theories raise important philosophical questions about human nature and human aspirations, society and history while at the same time he gave some original answers to these questions. Marx did not write a comprehensive book on philosophy neither did he provide any definite theory of philosophy. His critique of traditional philosophy contains his philosophical outlook.

Marx was a materialist because he formulated a materialist concept of history according to which the basis of all social institutions and social consciousness is economic structure of society, and that social reality determines social consciousness. He was a dialectician because he applied dialectics as a definite method of philosophy to find out objective as well as internal contradiction of society. According to his materialist dialectics, nothing is static or unchangeable, nothing is final or eternal; everything changes and develops

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according to the law of dialectics (law of motion). Marx's materialism (historical materialism) is not a metaphysical theory of history like that of Hegel. It is an empirical hypothesis which is called a philosophy of history. His dialectics is not based on abstract concepts like Hegel's idealistic dialectics rather it is based on concrete reality. He states that the premises from which we begin are not based on random choice or personal whims, but on real premises from which abstraction can be made only in the imagination. They are the real individuals, their activity and their material conditions of life. These premises can thus be established in a purely empirical way (Marx-Engels, 1976). Marx bears the legacy of philosophical traditions, particularly of Hegel's dialectics and Feuerbach's materialism. He sees himself as heir to these two philosophical traditions. In many places he expressed his adherence to materialism and his opposition to idealism. He also distinguished his materialism from earlier materialism and his dialectics from that of Hegel. Marx rejected Feuerbach's mechanical method but accepted his materialism as the basis of his philosophical theory. He rejected Hegel's idealism but accepted his dialectics as a method of explaining change, motion and development of the objective world.

It would be appropriate to consider Marx as a philosopher of social revolution. For him social change can be brought about by social revolution, not by social reform or moral criticism. He quotes, 'All forms and products of consciousness cannot be dissolved by mutual criticism, by revolution into self-consciousness, or transformation into 'apparitions', 'specters', 'whimsies', etc., but only by the practical overthrow of the actual social relations which gave rise to this idealist humbug; that not criticism but revolution is the driving force of history, also of religion, of philosophy and all other kind of theory (Marx-Engels, 1976).

3.3. Critique of Capitalism and Traditional Morality

Marx's critique of capitalism in his different writings and his conception of communism in his Critique of the Gotha Programme entertain certain basic philosophical issues like objective contradiction, internal contradiction, exploitation, alienation, human nature, nature of human relations, justice, equality, distribution etc. He applied his materialism to society, particularly to capitalist society of his time and he analyzed the nature of capitalist society and discovered the law of surplus value as the law of motion and development of capitalism. Two mutually contradictory classes exist in this society-the capitalist and the worker. The relation between the capitalist and the worker is a relation of exploitation and alienation. Capitalism is a society based on exploitation and economic

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inequality. The worker creates surplus value through his surplus labour and it is appropriated by the capitalist according to the law of capitalist economy. Additionally the worker's labour power is mixed with the commodity and he no longer belongs to it. The worker himself has been turned into a commodity. He loses his right to the commodity produced by his own labour. This is how the worker loses his own self and suffers from the problem of alienation. He does not belong to his work so he does not enjoy his work.

Exploitation and alienation are the two main defects of capitalism. The root of these problems lies in the internal contradiction of the capitalist society. This is the contradiction between capital and labour, contradiction between the ownership of private property and the social character of production. Capitalist society is based on the ownership of private property which in turn causes economic disparity in this society and exploitation and alienation arise out of this disparity. Human relations in the capitalist society have been turned into a relation of buying and selling of labour power, i.e. relations of transactions. The capitalists buy the labour-power of the workers, while the workers are forced to sell their labour-power. Thus human relations in this society have been turned into commercial relations and this is inhuman, and the man's outlook has become shopkeepers' outlook.

The concepts of exploitation and alienation are centrally important in Marxian liberation philosophy. The presence of exploitation in a society provides a ground for moral criticism, that exploitation is wrong and exploiters are morally condemnable and hence it ought to be abolished. Exploitation can provide the exploited with a ground for taking individual or collective action against the system. The notion of exploitation carries a very specific meaning in Marx's thought. In his sense, a person is exploited if he performs more labour than what is necessary to produce the goods that he consumes. Conversely, a person is an exploiter if he works fewer hours than are needed to sustain his consumption. For there to be exploiters, there must also be others who are exploited. But the converse need not be true. From the ethical point of view, exploitation cannot be a fundamental moral concept. One of the important causes of exploitation is the unequal distribution of wealth. Marx's critique of capitalism entertains the concept of exploitation in which the question of justice or injustice arises. It is unfair or unjust that some would be able to earn an income without working, while others who work would be deprived of its benefits. Marx located the phenomena of alienation at the level of individuals. By 'alienation' he meant the lack of self-realization of the individuals. In this sense, alienation takes the form of an unsatisfied desire for self-realization, which could motivate people to create a society in which that desire could be satisfied. Marx preferred communism because it would abolish alienation. Under communism

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the self-realization of each and every individual would be possible i.e., each and every individual will live a good life. In Marx's thought alienation simply means the absence of opportunities for self-realization. He placed exclusive emphasis on the lack of opportunities for self-realization in capitalism. He also emphasized that capitalism creates the material basis for communism in which the full and free self-realization of each and every individual becomes possible.

Alienation is related to exploitation in the sense that it adds to exploitation a belief on the part of the workers that a capitalist has a legitimate claim on the surplus by virtue of his legitimate ownership of the means of production. The ownership is seen as legitimate appropriation of surplus. In his theory of alienation, Marx suggested that the capitalist exploitation alienated labour from the products. He condemned capitalism by virtue of an objective alienation (Rashid, 2017).

3.3.1. Historical Materialism as Scientific Philosophy

In *The German Ideology* Marx formulated his philosophy as the materialist conception of history (commonly known as historical materialism). His philosophy is called scientific because it provides a scientific theory of society, particularly of social change and development. Marx observed that the change and development of society took place in accordance with objective laws. The general theory of the motive force and the objective laws of social change are known as the materialist conception of history. Marx's materialism is a scientific philosophy in the sense that it explains society in its dialectical movement, i.e., in change, motion and development of society. He discovered the law of dialectics in explaining change, motion and development of the objective world, nature, society and thought. As the natural scientists discovered the law of transformation of nature, Marx discovered the law of transformation of society from one stage to another. So, his materialism can be called scientific materialism by means of which he established a science of society. His scientific materialism is a way of explaining as well as solving the practical issues and problems of social life. The outcome of this activity and the conscious motives are conditioned by the laws of economic development which operate independently of the will or consciousness, i.e. objectively (Rashid, 2017).

Marx brought about a revolution in social science. He freed social science from idealist conception of history and based it on materialist conception. According to him, history is made neither by great men like kings, military leaders or scholars as the pre-Marxist sociologists thought nor by divine will or God as the pre-Marxist philosophers, particularly

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Hegel, observed. According to the idealist conception of history, society is ruled by divine will; God rules the world and the realization of his plans constitute world history. Marx freed history of human thought from idealism by formulating the principal postulate of historical materialism which stated, 'Social being determines social consciousness' (Marx-Engels, 1976). Social being encompasses the material life of society, above all people's productive activity and the economic relations between them. Social consciousness includes the spiritual life of people, the ideas, theories and views which guide their ways of life and their activities.

Marx started with the premise that, 'life involves before everything else eating, drinking, housing, clothing and various other things. The first historical act is thus the production of the means to satisfy these needs, the production of material life itself' (Marx-Engels, 1976). From this it follows that material production forms the foundation upon which the state, institutions, the legal conceptions, art and religious ideas have been evolved. This is Marx's materialist understanding of history which is considered to be scientific. According to this understanding, people are the real makers of history and their labour produce all the material wealth. This materialist conception of history or historical materialism is concerned with the study of society and the laws of its development. These laws are objective, i.e., independent of man's consciousness like the laws of nature. Laws of society are different from the laws of nature. While the laws of nature reflect the operations of blind, spontaneous forces, the laws of society are manifested through people's conscious activity in which they set themselves definite aims and work to achieve them. The laws of society are also studied by other social sciences which study a certain group of social phenomena. But Marx's historical materialism studies the more general laws of social development. The development of society has unique features which distinguish social changes from natural events. The essential feature lies in the fact that society is composed of conscious human beings. Objective laws cannot be discovered in society as in nature. In nature everything is determined in accordance with natural laws, but in society, what happens is determined by people's conscious aims. According to historical materialism, material relations are the determinative factors of social development. It is the totality of these production relations that constitutes the economic structure of society, the base. Each society has its own base. No base can appear until the corresponding material conditions, the productive forces are necessary for its birth. Once it arises, the base plays a tremendous part in the life of society. The base is important because it serves as the real foundation upon which the superstructure arises (political, legal, philosophical, moral and religious views). The superstructure also plays a very important role in social development. Arising on a definite economic basis, it

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ultimately expresses the attitude of people to this basis. Various ideas help people to influence the development of productive forces (Rashid, 2017).

The superstructure is brought into being by the base and is inseparably bound up with it thus it depends on the base. The base of a class society has its contradictions. The economic base of capitalism contains antagonism between the capitalist and the working class; hence, the superstructure also contains contradictions. It includes the ideas and institutions of different classes. The ideas and institutions of the class which dominate prevail economically. Under capitalism the capitalist ideas dominate economically so that the capitalist ideas and institutions prevail and are used by them against the working class. A close reading and observation will show that there are three guiding principles of Marx's historical materialism as follows:

Social development is regulated by objective laws (like science).

Views and institutions, political, cultural and ideological developments arise on the basis of the development of the material life of society and

The ideas and institutions which arise on the basis of conditions of material life play an active role in the development of the material life.

3.3.2. Class Philosophy

Marx brought about a revolution in the history of philosophical thoughts by providing an alternative view of philosophy. He observed that philosophy could not be isolated from society. In other words, there cannot be any philosophy in isolation from social reality. Thus he provided us with the idea of class philosophy. Philosophy emerged with the division of society into classes. In a class society, philosophy means the philosophy of a class. This class nature of philosophy became evident from the very day society was divided into classes. So, philosophy in a class divided society cannot be independent of the class. Now the question arises how did class and class philosophy emerge? Men had to go for work or production for survival and in this process working relations, i.e. relations of production among them were established. At one stage surplus value was created from relations of productions, ownership of private property from surplus value, class contradiction from ownership of private property and from there to class consciousness. As a result of class consciousness there was an emergence of class philosophy. Every philosophy in a class society reflects a class outlook. For example, dialectical materialism reflects the outlook of the working class, while idealism and mechanical materialism expresses the outlook of the bourgeoisie class. Philosophy is usually a world outlook which deals with the most general account of the nature of the world

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and man's place and destiny in it. Everybody has some kind of philosophy, and is influenced by some philosophical views even though they have never learned to discuss them, nor they have thought them out for themselves and formulate them.

When the society was divided into classes i.e. ever since the dissolution of the primitive communes (that is to say, throughout the entire period of human history to which the history of philosophy belongs), then the various views which arose in the society always expressed the outlook of various classes. It may, therefore, be concluded that the various systems of the philosophers also always express class outlook. In fact, they are nothing but the systematic working out and theoretical formulation of class outlook, or of the ideology of definite classes. So, philosophy is and always has been class philosophy. Man does not and cannot think in isolation from society, and therefore from class relations and class interests. As a world outlook; philosophy is an attempt to understand the world, mankind and man's place in the world. Such an outlook cannot be anything but the outlook of a class and the philosopher functions as the thinking representative of a class. Philosophers are not imported from some other planet, but are produced here on earth in existing class relations and class struggles. Therefore, there cannot be any philosophy that is independent of class, or which does not embody a class. According to class philosophy, the individuals composing the ruling class possess consciousness. They rule as a class, they also rule as thinkers, as producers of ideas and regulate the production and distribution of the ideas of their age. So their ideas are the ruling ideas of the age. During Aristocracy the concepts of honour, loyalty etc. were dominant. In Marx's words, 'The ideas of the ruling class are in every age, the ruling ideas, i.e., the class which is the dominant material force in society is at the same time its dominant intellectual force. The class which has the means of material production at its disposal, consequently also means of mental production. The ruling ideas are nothing more than the ideal expression of the dominant material relations' (Marx-Engels, 1976). In The Communist Manifesto Marx and Engels declared that 'the history of all hitherto existing society is the history of class struggles' and formulated the law of class struggle as the objective law of social development. According to class philosophy, class struggle is the driving force of social development, the dialectics of society. Class philosophy is considered to be a scientific philosophy in the sense that it reveals the laws of dialectics, i.e. the laws of motion and development of society. Class antagonism is the objective contradiction of society, which reveals the laws of dialectics. Contradiction between capital and labour (the capitalist and the working class) is the internal contraction of the capitalist society. This contradiction, for Marx, can be solved through social revolution (proletarian or socialist revolution). According

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to historical materialism, class society reflects class philosophy. Marx formulated the philosophy of the working class as materialist world outlook. He regarded the modern working class as a conscious revolutionary class and provided them with class philosophy as a revolutionary philosophy. Class philosophy provides the working class with the idea of emancipation from class exploitation, from economic disparity. The act is proletarian (or communist) revolution and the outlook is class outlook. The idea of emancipation implies the idea of an emancipating society (communist society), exploitation-free society. Class philosophy implies the idea of social revolution and a future communist society, a society based on humanity. Human emancipation, therefore, lies in the self emancipation of the working class. Thus, class philosophy appears to be a humanistic philosophy. Marx considered the relations of production as the foundation of his class philosophy. Class, for him is a theoretical concept, not a descriptive category. In other words, Marx was concerned to uncover the underlying realities of society, not merely to describe how things appeared to be. An individual's class, in his view, is defined by the position he occupies in the relations of production. Thus, class is seen by him as a social relationship. The antagonistic social relations are the heart of a class society according to Marx the labourer is regularly compelled to sell his labour-power in order to live as a member of the working class (Rashid, 2017).

3.4. The Four Important Marxian theories of economics

I will now briefly introduce the four main theories of economics by Karl Marx.

3.4.1. Marxian Theory of Capitalist Competition

Competition acts to reduce industry wide profits to the same rate. But capitalists strive to increase productivity in order to increase profits. Increased productivity usually involves increased reliance on capital, thus reducing proportion of variable capital and increasing rate of surplus value. Tendency from competition is therefore to increase fixed capital. Supply and demand cause fluctuation of market price from normal price, the latter being the price of production, but competition acts to bring these two prices into line. Here there is a contradiction between the supply and demand theory of value, cost-of-production theory of value, and Marx's labour theory of value (Dasgupta, 1984).

3.4.2. Marxian Theory of Wage Labor and Capital

Marx proposes two methods of circulating money and commodities,

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- a) Commodity sold / money received / money spent on new commodity (here the objective is to acquire a use-value).
- b) Commodity bought / money spent / commodity sold (here the objective is to increase one's holding of money, in other words to acquire exchange-value).

The later process involves an extraction of surplus value by the capitalist in the process. The surplus value is extracted from human labour, this being the commodity purchased in the first half of the transaction. When human labour is 'consumed' (i.e. when workers work) their use value is that they produce exchange value. The amount of exchange value produced net is then appropriated by the capitalist when the second half of the transaction is completed. Surplus value arises because labour is only ever paid by its subsistence wage. It can be increased by extending the working day, or by reducing that part of the working day required to meet labourers' subsistence requirements. The degree of exploitation is measured by the rate of surplus value (surplus value divided by the amount of variable capital employed). Surplus value does not equal the rate of profit because it excludes any measurement of fixed capital (Dasgupta, 1984).

3.4.3. Marxian Theory of Rent

Marx asks where gifts of nature obtain an exchange-value. He develops a theory of rent to answer this question. One theory is that rent is the payment to capital that is invested to make land productive. Marx rejects this theory since it doesn't explain why land in which no capital has been invested still accrues rent, and also because he sees it as an attempt simply to justify rent with reference to another capitalist institution (that of rent on money capital). A second theory is that differential rents arise because of the different fertility of various pieces of land. Differential rent is calculated by setting the exchange value of produce to be equal with the cost of producing on land used at the margin (thus making rent equal to zero here but positive on more fertile land). Marx rejects this theory since he subscribes to the labour theory of value. A third theory is that the aristocracy controls the land and that this monopoly gives rise to rent (this is the Historical school's interpretation of rent). The fourth theory is Marx's own theory, building on monopoly theory, stating that competition cannot occur with certain gifts of nature, because for example, the better productivity of some land above other land cannot be transferred as can the better productivity of one factory to another. Thus, the rate of profit to a landowner can remain above the economy-wide rate of profit and this 'surplus-profit' gives rise to absolute rent. Rent is a form of surplus value. Interest too is a form of surplus value. Money, like labour employed, allows the holder to derive a use-value

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from it that uses value being the fact that money (or labour) produces exchange-value. Only surplus value and wages are the sources of revenue in capitalist society (Dasgupta, 1984).

3.4.4. Marxian Theory of Economic Development

This is the most appealing section of Marx's work according to some commentators, mostly in *das Kapital*. The Law of Capitalist Accumulation states that capital employed by capitalists' increases overtime through the accumulation of the surplus value of larger workforces. The increased application of capital results in an increasing proportion of fixed capital in the production process, and requires the squeezing out of small capitalists in the familiar drive to achieve economies of scale. Joint-stock companies, bank and credit facilities all help to achieve this goal. Larger industrial units arise and the demand for labour increases, but technology demands a continual reduction of labour as a proportion of capital employed. As the proportion of fixed capital increases, the profit rate declines and mergers are sought by the capitalists in an effort to reduce industry costs. Industrial power is thereby focused in fewer hands, thus the Law of the Increasing Misery of the Working Class under capitalism. In due course an 'industrial reserve army' of unemployed is created, but higher unemployment means that goods remain unsold. Eventually an industrial crisis must occur. (Reporter, 2020)

3.5. How Marx advocates 'inclusive economics'

As we have seen from the above explanations, Marx dreamt of a society which would give a fair dignity of labour to its working class. The economics or financial inclusion forms the first step in this process. A point I would like to highlight here is that 'we' (the ruling class) are not doing any favour on 'them' (the labour class) by giving them the dignity of labour. In-fact the dignity is not some material thing or commodity which the ruling classes are offering the labour class but it is their dignity of being human which was taken away from them is being restored. Hence, there is no giver-receiver relation here. As humans, all are equal and have equal dignity and self respect just by their being human beings.

The press release by the Reserve Bank of India records, 'The value of FI Index for March 2022 stands at 56.4% vis-à-vis 53.9% in March 2021, with growth witnessed across all the sub-indices' (R.B.I, 2022). Hence it is showing a healthy growth of almost 2.5%, but as we have seen in Chapter 1, the official data cannot be considered as the gospel truth and the question remains as how much has the benefit trickled down the social ladder and

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whether the poor and marginalized have actually benefited from it. We shall deal with this issue in the next chapter in detail.

Marx's monetary theory attempted to establish the 'organic relation' of the various aspects of money, apparently lacking in the work of the Banking School. Put briefly, Marx started his analysis by positing money as the 'independent form of value', a commodity with its own value, and then proceeded to derive the functions of money. In deriving the later he linked the evolving forms of money to the performance of particular functions. Thus, gold coin and state fiat money were associated with the function of means of circulation. Credit money, a more developed and advanced type of money, was associated with the function of means of payment.

Financial inclusion means that individuals and businesses have access to useful and affordable financial products and services that meet their needs – transactions, payments, savings, credit and insurance – delivered in a responsible and sustainable way. It means that no segment of a population remains outside the influence of financial services due to their limited financial conditions and power. An RBI paper from 2013 showed that '51.4% of farmer households are financially excluded from both formal/ informal sources' and 'Overall, 73% of farmer households have no access to formal sources of credit'. Although the recent RBI reports show a fair growth, it is admitted that the financial inclusion hasn't reached the poorest of the poor and there exist many bottlenecks and challenges which need immediate attention. According to the World Bank's Global Financial Inclusion Database or Global Findex report (2017), 80% Indian adults have a bank account—27 points higher than the 53% estimated in the Findex 2014 round. The Findex 2017 report also estimates that 77% Indian women have bank accounts, against 43% and 26% respectively in 2014 and 2011 (Qazi, 2019). These figures, however, contrast with the statistics from the other spectrum. According to the same report, about 190 million adults in India do not have a bank account, making India the world's second largest nation in terms of unbanked population. Needless to mention that these 190 million people are from among the poorest of the poor, who for the want of proper documentation remain out of the reach of financial services. It is also understandable that these people have to be brought on board the financial service sector so that they can receive the benefits of the economic growth.

Marx through his theory of economic liberation advocates this very fact that the gains from the business ventures be distributed among the masses who toil for it rather than these gains being limited in the hands of a few wealthy corporate.

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In this sense I find that the Marxist ideology of liberation can guide the moral Shariah philosophy to reach these very marginalized and bring them in the financial service sector in India. It will thus, give us that multi-dimensional push which has been advocated by various government and non-government agencies working for the uplifting of the marginalized.

3.6. Conclusion from the Marxian economic ideals

Marx devoted his life to the cause of social revolution. He was committed to the philosophy of emancipation of man from exploitation, particularly of the working people from capitalist exploitation. He draws our attention because an understanding of his thought is essential for anyone who considers himself a social revolutionist, who wishes to do away with the exploitation and suffering that is built into the capitalist system whose law of motion he sought to uncover. The questions which Marx raised are still alive. Marx provided a scientific analysis of the nature of capitalism which shows that capitalism is an exploitative social system and its internal contraction will lead either to socialism or to barbarism, and that the only hope for humanity lies in the working class overthrowing the capitalist state and replacing it with their own rule. So, it is not possible to understand the real nature of capitalism without reading the philosophy of Marx (Rashid, 2017).

Capitalism has changed its form, but it has not changed its spots. It is still based on the exploitation of the working class, and liable to constant crisis. So, the conclusion Marx drew from this analysis that the working class would overthrow this system and would replace it with an exploitation-free (classless) society, is still relevant in the world today. Socialist revolution is an imperative if we are to change the world in the grip of economic depression. To that extent, Marx's ideas are more relevant today than they were before. Capitalism has tightened its grip of iron on every portion of the world. Now, this is the time to free the world from the domination of world capitalism to save world humanity and the choice is between workers' power or the 'common ruination of the contending classes'-between socialism or barbarism. Marx was always committed to the emancipation of the working class as well as to world humanity and conceived of the working class as the class whose own self-emancipation would also be the liberation of the rest of humanity. The socialist revolution for whose cause he devoted his life can only be the emancipation of the working class and the liberation of all the oppressed and exploited sections of society.

There is an important sense in which all of Marx's thought is still alive. Each one of Marx's major ideas is still very much worth studying. One reason for this is Marx's influence

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on the history of the twentieth century; his influence, in both theory and practice, is beyond measure. There are so many aspects of the current world and current world of ideas, that we would be unable to grasp without understanding and appreciating Marx's thought. This would be enough to justify our close attention to Marx. But there is much more than this. Consider, for example, the great philosophers like Plato, Aristotle, Descartes, Hume and Kant. Why do we read them? It is not because they have proved, or established any firm results, but because they are worth reading. The value of the greatest philosophers lies in their power, depth, inventiveness, insight, originality and systematic vision. Their works could have been created only if they believed that they had just discovered truth, or were on the verge of doing so. But there are things much more interesting than truth (Wolff, 2003). This way of understanding makes Marx's works worth reading and still alive. Even if Marx's grand theories may not be substantiated or proved to be true, his writings are so powerful that they cannot be abandoned to be unworthy. His work is full of insight and illumination. His major theories raise important philosophical questions about man and his hopes and aspirations, about society and history, which surely inspire his readers and provides food for thought for further thought. Marx also provided scientific solutions to the questions he raised. We may not agree with the solutions to the problems he identified but that does not make the problems go away; the problems remain in existence till today and we have to go back to Marx for a clear understanding of the nature of the problems. If philosophy is a thinking of thinking then Marx can be considered to be a thinker of the thinkers. It becomes evident when he says that reason has always existed but not always in a reasonable form. What he meant is a rational and scientific understanding of the world. So, we should read Marx to think about thinking, to get a rational and scientific understanding of the world for practical purpose, i.e for the purpose of changing the world (Rashid, 2017).

In conclusion I would say that Marx is one of the most practical thinkers and his theory of liberation is unique in that it actually leads to action rather than being a mental exercise. Marxist ideals of liberation of working class must be remembered yet the revolution should come in the form of change of attitude and its' practical on the ground implementation, rather than a revolt as he suggests. I will further elaborate on this topic in the next chapter.

Chapter Four

The Philosophy of Economics

4.1. Is profit generated the sole criteria for judging the success of public sector banking in India?

India is a unique country because the demography and cultural diversity it covers are unique only to India. As such it is very difficult to have one size fits all solution to every problem or issue facing us. Our Constitution is a masterpiece written by the best minds of the late century and they have succeeded in creating a just and civil society in India to a large extent. Every institution in our country functions to the expected standard but for the political and bureaucratic meddling which can be unhealthy most of the time. Our judiciary, defense and finance systems were largely untainted and were considered among the best in this side of the world. This has changed with the socio-political-economic situation prevalent in our country.

As clarified in Chapter 1; the largest and the best among the Indian banks were nationalized in 1969 with the specific intent to make them facilitators of government aid and policies for the people. This was a very noble and praiseworthy decision because the then policy-makers saw through the loopholes and limitations in private sector banks with respect to handling such roles. A private sector bank is administered with the sole aim of making profit and such there is a limitation in its risk taking capacity and social responsibility. The governing body or management cannot run all their bank projects on 'no-profit, no-gain' policy. Even the so called 'Corporate Social Responsibility' is limited in its funding and outreach and limited to mostly semi-urban or selected rural areas. There are also issues about the lack of accountability and integrity the way these CSR funds are disbursed and reports made. Also the private banks would not work to implement government schemes which do not pertain to their particular segment of customers. Hence the government banks were expected to be lead integrators of 'financial inclusion in India' in doing so it was logically expected that they would have to forego the sole criteria of making profit but look at the wider progress and development of the society. This is something which the public sector banks have done in the past; they have implemented all government schemes for the people without thought of profit. Example, when a particular saving account scheme was launched by the Indian government (PM-JAY), the most number of accounts were opened by the public sector banks, this has helped to increase the percentage of saving account holders in

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India to about 77% according to globaleconomy.com. I was working as a Branch Manager in a rural branch of the Union bank of India, so based on my experience let me analyze the situation. We opened more than 850 saving bank accounts with zero-balance. All these accounts were given 'personalized debit cards' which are usually given to account holders who maintain a minimum balance of ₹.5000/-. These cards are printed in only two high security companies in India (I will not divulge their locations here) and dispatched through registered post. For increased security, the card and the PIN are dispatched separately. Only 2 cards are sent per envelope to prevent the impact of damage due to loss in transit. Now all these charges are borne by the bank. Hence, we were creating loss assets for our bank. Now, it is not that the top management did not know this fact, in-fact they saw the overall impact and the total loss emanated from the entire nation. However, they chose to continue this activity as it was mandated by the government. The estimated loss in this venture would have been in lakhs of rupees. I could give examples of several other schemes which were in-fact loss making but were nevertheless implemented due to government mandates by the public sector banks. The private sector banks cannot be enforced by the government but were asked to do their best in implementing these schemes, which they did on a selective basis. The impact of these schemes was felt in the financial statements of the public sector banks with the result that there was a sharp effect on their profit. Again as a majority stakeholder, the government of India dictates the percentage of profit these banks must earn, this again is a unique concept only in India as nowhere in the world do the stakeholders have the authority to dictate and demand the percentage profit which a company must earn for their benefit. The fall of profit of the public sector banks was blamed on the apathy and slothful attitude of the bank staff and negatively impacted their salary and in few cases the transfers of the officers. The government remained silent on the actual cause of the loss resulting from their own policies and schemes. It was decided to merge the banks and later privatize these institutions if the losses continue.

This brings me to my question, 'Is profit generated the sole criteria for judging the success of public sector banking in India?' the answer is a resounding no! It is the public sector banks which not only face the brunt of impractical government policies, but also bear the losses in their balance sheet without hesitation. They have the resources to bear the impact of such risky ventures and implement the government policies without causing public outrage. As such it would be foolishness on the part of the government judge the success of public sector banking in India based on the sole criteria of profit generated by these institutions. The government should realize that it itself is one of the main causes of loss due

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to its unnecessary meddling in the financial sphere of the nation's economy. It should also understand that if these institutions are privatized then there will not be any other financial organization in India which will implement its financial policies with such zeal and passion with full knowledge of the risks and losses involved. The public sector banks are the proverbial, 'golden egg laying goose' for the government.

Also we have to understand and resolve the issue of branding the public sector banks as 'profit making' and/or 'social responsibility' institutions, as both of these factors can go together only to a certain limit and then the institution has to decide between one of the two. It can either be a profit making institute or an institute which is concerned with the implementations of social responsibilities. If the government wants them to make profit then it should not unnecessarily burden them with social responsibilities and vice versa. The current scenario is that the public sector banks are torn between these two roles and there is no official clarity on their roles.

The role of the public sector banks in nation building has been extremely vital and cannot be ignored. These banks need to be strengthened and empowered to continue their duties with better decision making powers and non-interference by political entities for personal or electoral gains. Also the Public sector bank management needs to be constantly aware of the fact that their role as an organization has been in social empowerment through preferential importance given to the weaker sectors of our country like agriculture, MSME, educational loans and other priority sector lending and saving schemes tailor-made for the targeted sector. Also we need products with more flexibility in repayment options and incentives for regular repayment so as to encourage the farmers and small businesspeople to repay their loan in a time-bound manner. This will also help them as their income from their primary activities is not fixed, but sporadic in these sectors and depended upon a lot of external factors unlike the established businesses and essential products and services.

For fulfilling this role in a better way, I propose that the concepts of the liberation philosophy of Karl Marx be applied to the ideals of Shariah banking and this new amalgamated model of banking codes of conduct be used in Indian banking sector to guide our banking ethics and mode of conduct.

I have elaborated the concepts of Islamic banking and Marxian economy in chapters 2 and 3 respectively. In this segment I shall try to combine the two philosophies and derive the best qualities of the two from the point of view of liberation and ethical philosophy and see how we can use them for ethical banking option for developing economies like India. I shall first elaborate the philosophies which define the workings of these two thought processes.

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4.2. How the philosophy of Marxian economics can compliment Shariah banking system in making it an ethical banking option for developing economies like India

When we speak of Shariah banking, people immediately think of banking for the Muslims or the believers of Shariah code of conduct. Hence, there is an immediate feeling of hostility and suspicion on what I am trying to expound. As clarified earlier, I have taken the concept of Shariah banking based purely on philosophical perspective. I shall now bring out the concept of Shariah banking as a science and its philosophy of operation, at the same time I shall also elaborate as how it can be combined with Marxist liberation philosophy and applied in the case of a secular country like India, which is not an Islamic, nor a Marxist nation.

4.2.1. The concept of Shariah banking as a Science

Shariah banking works on the philosophy of the Islamic scriptures as recorded in the Quran and Hadith. The world economy is divided into two main branches of economic thought, the capitalist economy model introduced by Adam Smith and the Marxist/Socialist economy model introduced by Karl Marx. These two economic models highlight two different methodologies undertaken by nations in solving their economic problems and define their philosophy of economy. The capitalist model advocates freedom while the socialist model advocates equality. Then we have a 'mixed-economy' model which uses a combination of both these models for economic growth and was used by countries like India. Similarly, we have a new methodology called Islamic economic model based on Islamic principles which saw a beginning and growth after the WW2. Researchers have done a lot of studies to define the Islamic economy. Literally Islamic Economics consists of two words namely economics and Islam. The word economy comes from the Greek *eicos* (household) and *nomos* (rule or law). While the characters give different interpretations, including: Muhammad Abdul Manan (1997), Islamic economics is a science that discusses and studies people's economic problems based on Islamic values. Metwaly in Furqani (2018), Islamic economics can be defined as a science that studies the behavior of Muslims in an Islamic society that follows the sources of Islamic law, namely the Quran, Hadith, Ijma' and Qiyas. Hasanuzzaman in Tahir (2017), Islamic Economics is the science as well as the application of sharia rules that prevent *kedzaliman* in obtaining material resources so as to create human satisfaction and allow them to carry out the commandments of God and society.

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Ahmad (1994), Islamic economics is a systematic effort to understand economic problems and human behavior in its relationship to the issue is reviewed from an Islamic perspective (Khoerulloh & Hidayah, 2021).

There have been several previous studies conducted in this regard by scholars and intellectuals in order to liberate the Islamic economy from being purely theological to making it a science with its empirical knowledge and methodology. Chief study among them is research conducted by (Ztf & Suwardana, 2002) in his research explained that to make the Islamic economy a science must be accompanied by the Islamic economic system itself. He mentioned that science would not stand alone without a system being run. Science will be formed whenever it can be proven empirically. Then (Hartono, 2011) explained that the Islamic economic system is the solution to the economic crisis that befell the Europeans. The capitalist economic system used by the Western nations failed repeatedly, this failure was marked by an economic crisis in Europe. Thus, Hartono provided a solution to the economic crisis, namely the Islamic economic system (Khoerulloh & Hidayah, 2021).

I am looking at Islamic economy as a science and a philosophy, a science which can be tested theoretically and empirically. An economic system that has certain characteristics different from other economic systems based on the ethical and liberative thought process can be a solution to the economic problems of countries like India because the Islamic economic system is guided by the moral teachings of Quran. Looking and understanding the Quran as an inspired book which can provide us with scientific rather than dogmatic understanding of ethics is very important in case of Secular nation like India. It will also help us in being open to the requirements of our financial system and to make it more accessible to the poor and the needy, in a logical way; something which a purely dogmatic understanding will not be able to do. This is because dogma or theology works in limited constraints of the scripture and there is a limitation to its openness to the changing times and circumstances.

If I say that we look at Islamic Economics as a Science then the question arises as how and what will make it an acceptable solution to the non-Islamic and rational thinkers. Western scientists have the view that a science must be structured on realities that are empirical, measurable and can be proven scientifically through the verification process, if the assumptions are built only on the truth of value and cannot be verified; then the assumption cannot be categorized as a science (Nurrohman, 2012). Frankly speaking, looking at the view of western scientists who put forward empirical principles; which are presumed to be free from the value of an assumption, Islamic Economics in some points is more suitable to be established as a doctrine than to be established as a science. Also the Islamization of

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economics seems to be done ‘dichotomously’ between the conceptual (theoretical) and the empirical dimensions. In the conceptual part, Islamic economists attempt to find Islamic justification based on Quranic verses over certain theories, while in the empirical part, Islamic economists just utilize and apply the common statistical methods into an Islamic/Muslim case, assuming no contradiction to Islamic heritage. Islamic economics heavily depends on conventional economics especially the dominant neo-classical paradigm as far as the empirical part of economics is concerned (Haneef & Furqani, 2011). Economics and Islam have opposite traits. Economics is clearly a scientific study that can be used to solve a problem and can be verified the truth. However, Islam is a religion that contains a set of normative rules, derived from the Divine in the manifestation of the Quran and Hadith whose truth can only be measured through spiritual values that may not be recognized by people who do not believe in it (Nurrohman, 2012). The core problem of the lack of acceptance of Islamic economics as an Islamic economic science is because it is supposed to be full of normative values so much so that some aspects are abstract so that it is not value-free and cannot be proven empirically. Foucault said science is controlled by the dominant forces that control the region whether in the form of religion, politics or economics. Through mastery, ‘truth’ is determined. A particular country, community or civilization throughout history can ‘impose the truth’. Therefore there is no science that is neutral and interest-free (A. Zaman, 2012). Because all science is ideologically charged, as socialist economics contains Marxist ideology and mainstream economics contains a narrow ideology or free market, in fact both sciences contain values and normative assumptions as well as descriptive assumptions. The Islamic Economic System even though it contains normative assumptions cannot be judged directly as not being a science just for reasons that it is not free of value.

Islamic economics is a scientific study that examines human behavior in meeting its needs based on the Quran and Hadith. The word Shariah refers more to normative laws, while the word Islam has a broader meaning as a religion (Khan, 2013). The word Muamalah and economy is different where the former means exchange or empowerment of property based on agreement. While the economic word Iqtishod al-Islamiy has a broader meaning that is to meet the needs based on justice. Islamic economics is not accepted as a science because it is considered not value-free and contains normative arguments (Mahomed, 2013). Whereas the Quran and Hadith that become the basis in the Islamic economy contains many descriptive arguments that can be proven by modern knowledge. Foucault says that there is no neutral science; there is always a tendency from a scientific study to an ideology. From this exposure

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it can be concluded that Islamic economics should not be viewed as merely a doctrine alone but also as a science (Khoerulloh & Hidayah, 2021).

4.2.2. Islamic Economy as a System

I shall now explain how the Islamic economy is a systematic approach towards financial liberation and not just a simple doctrinal/ theological thesis. It is a unique blend of divine guidelines in the form of Quran and Hadith as well as practical humanistic view as it advocates human freedom and prosperity of human life. Faith and belief in moral system influences not just personal but also social, political and financial outlook of a person. Hence the system of Shariah banking has the following characteristics:

- a) Wealth is a deposition from God: Hence Islam does not prohibit personal/ private property, but holds human beings accountable for its fair and just usage. It also states that others rights are not disturbed by the earning of one's wealth, i.e. fair wage and labor policy as well as ethical business competition is to be followed.
- b) Faith, Shariah and morality as the foundation: Islamic economics advocates that integrity with spiritual values and economic activities can become worship. This is reflected in the prohibition of ownership and use of property that can harm others, the prohibition of fraud in transactions and the prohibition of hoarding (Khoerulloh & Hidayah, 2021).
- c) The balance between individual and public interest: Islam does not recognize absolute rights and absolute freedom. An economic activity should not be directed solely towards serving personal interests while ignoring the greater good of the community.
- d) Guarantee of individual freedom: Every individual in Islam is guaranteed with certain restrictions because in fact the property is a deposition from God and emphasized that this freedom is not absolute. However, there are prohibitions aimed at creating justice in the economic order of the community. This is in contrast to the capitalist economic system that gives free reign to the private sector, and is different from the socialist economic system that attaches great importance to the public interest.
- e) The existence of state authority, The state has the authority and obligation to help improve the lives of its citizens. This principle is different from the socialist economic system that gives full authority to the state and vice versa in the capitalist economy the authority of the state is severely restricted.
- f) Provide guidance on consumption and investment: Islamic economics provides strict guidelines on utilization and the mode of investment of the wealth so that it can be used for the good of the society as well as generating profit for the individuals.

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Hence, we see that the Islamic economic system gives very practical guidelines about the usage of the wealth. So, I conclude that it is a systematic approach to the economics and not simply based on a dogma or theology. We also see that these instructions are easy to be adopted by non-Muslims as well as atheists and agnostics as they have underlying principle of betterment of the entire humanity.

4.2.3. The Philosophy of Islamic Banking

The Islamic economic system focuses on balance and justice. Property ownership consists of individual, general, and state ownership in a balanced manner, so it is expected to create the welfare of the people evenly and of course the moral value to all economic actors. Whereas the capitalist and socialist economies fail to grasp it in a certain sense, the capitalist economic system talks about its needs and tools. The system is built with three basic frameworks. First, the scarcity of goods and services, goods and services available are not able to meet all the diverse human needs. Second, the value of an item produced. Third, prices in production, consumption, and distribution where a price is a controlling tool in a capitalist economy (Khoerulloh & Hidayah, 2021).

There has been a constant clash of values between the Socialist and the Capitalist models of economies. In fact, many mention that the emergence of the Socialist economic system is a form of resistance to the injustice suffered by society because of the Capitalist economic system and the mistakes that occur in it. There are several principles that exist in this Socialist economy. First, realize the real similarities. Second, remove individual ownership in whole or in part. Third, organize production and distribution collectively. The Economic System explains the distribution of wealth and its ownership, as well as how to conduct transactions against it and so on. This explanation means they follow a certain view of life. Therefore, the economic system in the Islamic view is certainly different from the economic system in the view of both the Socialism and Communism, and also in the view of Capitalists. Because, each follows a certain ideological life view, which is different from Economics. Economics discusses its production and quality and how to determine and improve its facilities. This is universal for all nations, which is not specifically based on a particular ideology, but is rather like any other science (Khoerulloh & Hidayah, 2021).

For example, in the view of ownership, ownership in the Capitalist System is clearly different from the Socialist System and different from the Islamic System. As for how to improve production, it concerns a reality that is scientific. This is the same for all human beings, in terms of looking at it, although the understanding of ideology can differ. Islam's

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view on wealth issues is different from Islam's view on the issue of wealth utilization (Iqbal & Mirakhor, 2011). According to Islam, the means that provide usability are its own problems, while the acquisition of usability is another problem. Therefore, wealth and human power, both are wealthy, as well as advice that can provide usefulness or benefits. Thus, the position of both in the view of Islam, in terms of existence and production in this life is different from the position of utilization and the procedure of obtaining its benefits. Therefore, Islam also intervenes in the problem of the utilization of wealth in a clear way.

Hence, Islam clearly has a practical approach towards economics it allows individual freedom like a Capitalist economy while also advocating the prudent use of wealth and its application for the help of the needy through instruments like Zakat. Hence, it is a practical approach and not simply doctrinal.

4.2.4. The Liberation philosophy of Marx and its application to Shariah Economics of banking

I have explained briefly about the philosophy of Karl Marx in Chapter 3, hence I shall limit myself in elaborating his ideas again. In this sub-section I would instead write about how the Islamic world, particularly its financial system was influenced by the liberation philosophy.

The origin of Liberation theology as we know began from a few Catholic theologians/philosophers/social reformers in Latin America. This was a response to the traditional view of the Church in understanding the concept of God. Gutiérrez in fact stated that the Church would not have an authentic theology of liberation until the oppressed can express themselves independently and creatively as children of God. A Muslim thinker in Indonesia, Abdurrahman Wahid, was greatly influenced by Gutiérrez's philosophy and adapted it to the Indonesian particularly Islamic context. I shall use the same liberation philosophy of Abdurrahman Wahid as a base of my thesis comparing it with that of Marx; both, in context of Shariah banking. Liberation theology is an understanding of the role of religion in the social sphere. In other words, liberation theology is an attempt to contextualize religious teachings and values on the concrete problems around them (Sigmund, 1990). The Christian Liberation theology was a result of the contextual hermeneutics of the Bible in answer to the socio-economic-political problems facing the Latin America. After interpreting the messages in the Bible based on Jesus' actions defending and helping the weak, sick, and oppressed, it was felt that the role of religion should also be like that. In Christianity, this is the responsibility of the Church as a religious institution that has influence and duty, both

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towards the congregation, the community in which it lives, and to its government. The values that emerge are usually seen from humanity and justice. Violations of these values in several countries have raised concerns among activists in liberation theology. For example, Christians with the teachings of Christology interpret that Christ is a person who is present in chaotic situations and brings deliverance to the small and oppressed people. From this, Christians follow Jesus' example and oppose injustice. They feel obligated to continue the work of God that they worship (Sirait, 2020).

In the Christian world, as written by Löwy's book (Lowy, 1988), liberation theology is a synthesis between the religious movement and the Marxism which has always been believed to be two perspectives that are impossible to unite. Few of the liberation theologians want the church to return to its function as the liberator of the oppressed. This refers to the history of the founding of the church itself, which has lasted two thousand years which is more accepted by the poor or the oppressed, and the church's concern for the poor is nothing new. They paid special attention to the Exodus section 'as a paradigm of the struggle for the liberation of enslaved people'. In its social activities, the church was still paying attention to the poor. But the approach used is merely generosity or tending towards being paternalistic. This approach was opposed and changed by liberation theology. One of his doctrines states: 'Poor people can no longer continue to be targets of generosity, but they must be individuals who are capable of their liberation. Assistance or fatherly assistance must be replaced with collective solidarity; poor people must be able to determine their destiny'. Therefore, Löwy concludes that for the theologians of liberation, Marxism seems to be a systematic, concise and comprehensive explanation of the causes of poverty. Poverty as a humanitarian crisis occurs not only because the people who are less active in trying to prosper. Liberation Theologians looked towards Marxism not only as a scientific analysis tool but also as a utopian will for social change. Hence, Lowy comments that they were more Marxist than those claiming to be 'pure Marxists' (Lowy, 1988).

In Islam, freedom is a nature (fitrah) given by God. When one denies the other powers, it means he is already in the context of freedom. The conception of freedom in Islam is based on monotheism labeled as celestial religion of monotheism. As Faruqi said, monotheism is considered as a worldview and the principle of the social order should be able to answer worldly problems, like political, social and economic as well as divinity (Al-Faruqi, 1982). Islam is no longer interpreted at the level of mere ritual formality, but it is oriented and driven by a spirit of humanity. Prophets like Noah, Musa, David, 'Isa (Jesus) and Muhammad were each inspired by religion and humanity (Al-Faruqi, 1962).

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Abdurahman Wahid, an Indonesian figure, once fought for the rights of the poor people from the arrogance of the government in 1980. He is also known as a figure who fought for pluralism, which is an attitude of respecting human freedom in religion. This issue was conveyed through seminars, scientific meetings and even through changes in state law in Indonesia. He was an avid believer in Marxist ideology and criticized Capitalist ideology. He believes that while in Christian world the theology of liberation meant motivating the class struggle and giving dignity to the marginalized, in Islamic world so far the foundation has only been implemented in the structure of fiqh, like prayer, fasting, ṣadaqah, while the essence of the fiqh order is not implemented in the social sphere. In fact, according to Asghar Ali Engineer, liberation theology was born to take a role in defending oppressed groups, both oppression in religious and political matters. Referring to the above problems, then Islam should transform itself into social change. Islam does not only emphasize the formality of ritual worship but also must pay attention to social order such as justice and humanity (Engineer, 1990). It should be that Islam becomes a system of belief that animates every Muslim to fight various oppressions. Islam frees humans from alienation by making liberation theology a method of its movement. Hence, it should transcend the foundation of the society, which is its economic system according to Marx.

The emergence of Islam's transformative function cannot be separated from the fact that this religion has from the beginning kept two mutually reinforcing dimensions. Islam as a religion that contains ideal principles, at the same time emphasizes action and liberation. This perfect combination of theory and action found its complete form within the framework of the vertical relationship between man and God, and the horizontal relationship between man and other creatures. Seeing such teachings, it can be imagined that Islam cannot be completely separated from the social empirical problem, in practice, Islam is always involved with interests outside of itself. Indeed, religion in this context seems to be 'value-free', thus opening up opportunities for change. The notion of 'interests' can be broadly elaborated, including the desires of state institutions in-progress projects, or the will of religious leaders to change from unsatisfactory conditions imposed by the state. Muslims are asked to determine attitudes between supporting the status quo or oppose it. At this point, the discussion about the conception of liberation (based on religion) in Wahid's thought found its relevance.

Islam which has grounded its culture can finally rise to the level of the main values (Weltanschauung) of Islam itself, which is centered on justice, equality and democracy. These three values become the image of Islam because with its Islam protects the five basic

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human rights, namely, protection of the right to life, thought, belief, personal property rights, and the sanctity of the family. So, the value of justice, equality before the law, and democracy are structural conditions that must be realized to move the protection of these basic human rights. Something is interesting about Wahid's approach, namely his rejection of the supplementary approach that many do by activists who carry on behalf of religion (Islam). The transformative value of Islam itself is considered important, because some Muslim thinkers take the ideology of liberation from outside of Islam, while on the other hand there is the ignorant attitude of the clergy (at least religious institutions) to deal with social problems. In fact, in Wahid's view, the non-secular attitude of Islamic behaviour is important because it can provide orientation and development theory from the treasures of religious teachings (Wahid, 2006).

According to Wahid, the teachings of Islam are liberation of humanity. Historically, Islam has emerged as a criticism of the injustices found in the Arabian merchant community in the past, though not directly. This is the reason why Islam concentrates on formulating practical ways to overcome such injustice (Barton, 2005). According to Wahid, indigenization of Islam is an understanding which always considers local needs in formulating religious laws without changing the law itself. Indigenization of Islam is not an attempt to leave norms for the sake of culture, but so that norms accommodate cultural needs by sticking to the understanding of the shariah.

Hence, liberation philosophy aims to bring out Islam from being a purely dogmatic faith based religion to a practical praxis oriented socially relevant movement. By doing this the Shariah law is not moving away from its fundamentals, rather, it is going back to its fundamentals which advocate the liberation of humanity and opposing injustice. In this way the liberation philosophy of Karl Marx will help Shariah system of finance to become more realistic and alive to the needs of the poor and the marginalized.

4.2.5. Some issues in application of Liberation philosophy in Islam

As I have explained how the liberation philosophy of Karl Marx will help in making the Shariah Banking more practical and morally stronger. Now I shall list some issues which I foresee in application of Marxist liberation philosophy in Shariah Banking.

i) Should Islamic banking be developed as a faith based science, by including the global academic community and finance experts or keeping it limited to Muslim community?

This problem is more real than hypothetical because as we have seen from the above discussions on Shariah economics, there has always been a puritanical group claiming that

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inclusion of non-Muslim experts would lead to the dilution of Shariah principles. However, in the likely circumstances the suggestions of this group are considered then Islamic banking will not benefit from potential contributions of other scholars. It would impair intellectual growth of the subject. Islamic economics would remain a stunted social science that revolves around Muslims and is cut off from rest of the world. It would also restrict the message of Islam to Muslims only although Islam stands for betterment of the entire humanity.

ii) Relationship with conventional economics: Adopt, adapt or discard?

The rationale for creating Islamic economics as a social science must be based on positive reasoning the reason for accepting Islamic banking system should be more as a complementary to the existing banking systems. We must remember that the reason for bringing this new system into being is because bringing ethics into economics will take it back to its original track. Conventional economics was originally based on ethics derived from religion (Chapra, 2006). The most notable champion of ethics in economics was no one else than the father of modern economics, Adam Smith. While I favor bringing in these moral values, I do not agree in adopting overt religious precepts, because it may cause unease and alienation in a certain segment of population. Our aim is to create a financial ecosystem which is acceptable to everyone for the sole aim of bringing a solid ethical base in banking so that it accepts its role in nation and community building by supporting the weaker segments.

iii) Should it remain limited as a positive theory or be used to bring about a social change?

As we apply the liberation philosophy of Marx to the Shariah system of banking, we should remember that Marx was a practical philosopher; he wanted philosophy to move out from being a purely academic science into being an actual life changing activity. Hence it goes without saying that the new theory should be tested and applied on the ground level for the problem solution.

4.2.6. How Liberation philosophy of Marxism compliments and strengthens Islamic economics

The liberation philosophy of Marxism makes Islamic banking system more solid in the practical sense of term. Islamic economics is already based on a solid ethical foundation of the Islamic Scriptures. The liberation philosophy of Marxism only strengthens it by helping it to get actually involved in the real life issues of oppression and poverty and help to resolve them by playing a constructive role in the financial sphere of the country. In doing this Islamic banking is in-fact following the basic principles of Shariah. As mentioned earlier the ignorance and mediocrity of the Islamic clergy has resulted in Islamic faith to remain a

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dogmatic belief practice which hardly transcends the moral life of majority its adherents. A renewal of Islamic studies, and particularly Islamic financial studies based on contribution by academics and financial experts from around the world will help Islam to open up to the modern ideas and imbibe the progress made in the past few centuries. It will also bring a fresh awakening in the practice of morals as prescribed by the Quran and the Hadith. Similarly, by applying of Liberation philosophical aspects of Marxist economics to Islamic banking will solidify its base structures and therefore the super structures which arise on these base structures will be alive to the needs of the laborers, the farmers and the small entrepreneurs. This will give them their dignity as human beings and prevent the malpractices which have arisen due to capitalism like inhuman takeover of the minnows, taking disadvantage of farmers by commodity price manipulation, lay-offs of laborers due to varied reasons, minimum wage payments not being done in timely manner and so on. It should also be mentioned here that the application of Shariah rules to liberation philosophy of Marxism will make it more humane by making its hatred of oppressors as a redundant issue. As Shariah economics is rooted in Shariah scriptures which promote the human welfare and protection, so it follows that hatred and violence against the perceived enemies of the proletariat does not entail violence, rather empowering of the proletariat by making them available the financial means and assistance to rise above poverty and making them self-reliant. Hence the two systems will complement each other in ethical and moral standards.

4.2.7. A new philosophy of economic liberation- not Socialist, nor Islamic, but pan-human

The new philosophy which emerges from the amalgamation of the liberation philosophy of Marxism and Shariah banking will be humanistic in its outlook. I am proposing here an Islamic banking with Marxist economics at its core which will neither be only for the Muslims nor for the Marxists, but will be pan-human in a way that is advocated by both of these philosophies. It will be open for people of all faiths and the atheists, it will be open for the capitalists as well as the socialists, it will exteriorly resemble the banks we currently have in India in all aspects with the sole difference being that it will have as its primary vision the empowerment of the priority sector particularly, agriculture and MSMEs. This will be different from the current scenario where banking activities are extended to this sector merely due to government regulations, a sort of mechanical activity. While in Marxist-Shariah banking system the bankers/financers will not only provide the finances but also with other hand-holding activities in cooperation with like-minded organizations with the aim of

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empowerment of the beneficiaries. This approach will help in a holistic economic activity where the banks role is not simply limited with financing a project and receiving the income through repayments at a later date, rather the bank as a nodal agency will not only finance an agricultural or MSME activity, it will also look for other aspects which make the asset healthy, like training, application of modern technologies, providing the tools and machinery at affordable rates and finally even the marketing of the products by providing an online trading platform, a sort of commodities exchange where the farmers and the small entrepreneurs will deal directly with the processors or the wholesalers rather than the middle-men as in current scenario. This will ensure that the profits earned through the toil of the farmer reach him in the full, and that he gets the dignity of his labor. It will remove the middle-men from the equation in its entirety. This will also ensure that fewer of such loans become NPAs. As I have already explained, the main causes for NPAs in priority sectors is insufficient knowledge, climatic factors and markets determined by the middle-men and the corporate syndicate. For the insurance, we can apply the Islamic insurance facility of SUKUK, which will again enhance the cooperative spirit among the farmers while covering for the losses in any circumstances. The major transformation, which I feel this system will bring, is in the perspective of the bankers towards the farmers and the entrepreneurs. This will eradicate the superiority complex of bankers as doing a favor on the priority sector to being a part of the greater chain of human beings who are actively involved in making a difference in the lives of so many people. As a nodal agency, the banks should tie up with other government and non-government agencies who are actively involved in this work. I know that it will be impractical to suggest that the banker do the entire spectrum of activity in agriculture or MSME, he may not have the requisite knowledge and even the time for this additional responsibility. So he needs to be a facilitator between the beneficiary and the various organizations who will take up the specialized tasks. Active collaborations with agriculture and MSME training institutes, academic institutions, professionals in marketing and storage houses should all be brought together in a form of a web with the bankers being in the center, directing the beneficiaries to the required specialists. This is the Marxist-Shariah banking framework which I am proposing in this thesis.

Conclusion

In the conclusion, I would like to emphasize my research thesis in the following three points, viz.

Prioritizing the needs of the marginalized.

The public sector banks should not be judged solely on the criteria of profit earned.

The Comprehensive study and implementation of Shariah banking from the Marxist perspective of liberation will be a boon for a country like India.

a. Indian banking sector: prioritizing the needs of the marginalized

India is a unique country because the demography and cultural diversity it covers are unique only to India. As such it is very difficult to have one size fits all solution to every problem or issue facing us. Our Constitution is a masterpiece written by the best minds of the late century and they have succeeded in creating a just and civil society in India to a large extent. Every institution in our country functions to the expected standard but for the political and bureaucratic meddling which can be unhealthy most of the time. Our judiciary, defense and finance systems were largely untainted and were considered among the best in this side of the world. This has changed with the socio-political-economic situation prevalent in our country.

As clarified in Chapter 1; the largest and the best among the Indian banks were nationalized in 1969 with the specific intent to make them facilitators of government aid and policies for the people. This was a very noble and praiseworthy decision because the then policy-makers saw through the loopholes and limitations in private sector banks with respect to handling such roles. A private sector bank is administered with the sole aim of making profit and such there is a limitation in its risk taking capacity and social responsibility. The governing body or management cannot run all their bank projects on 'no-profit, no-gain' policy. Even the so called 'Corporate Social Responsibility' is limited in its funding and outreach and limited to mostly semi-urban or selected rural areas. There are also issues about the lack of accountability and integrity the way these CSR funds are disbursed and reports made. Also the private banks would not work to implement government schemes which do not pertain to their particular segment of customers. Hence the government banks were expected to be lead integrators of 'financial inclusion in India' in doing so it was logically expected that they would have to forego the sole criteria of making profit but look at the wider progress and development of the society. This is something which the public sector

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banks have done in the past; they have implemented all government schemes for the people without thought of profit.

Hence, the public sector banks' main role was/is the priority sector lending. As such this target should not be lost in the zeal for making profits. The public sector banks are an asset for the Indian government and the government should not use them for short term electoral gains by disbursing loans to the corporate that finance the particular political party, waiving off agricultural loans/ MSME loans in spite of favorable conditions etc. These political gimmicks cost the nation dearly and make the public sector banks the scapegoats of such failed policies. The public sector banks should be asked to focus on priority sector and the marginalized sections of our country. They can also serve the other sector but not on priority scale. The public sector banks must imbibe the liberation philosophy of Marxism and the principles of Shariah banking and using this as a moral footing, make the priority sector their main area of focus, use the best of their manpower and resources for the cause of the upliftment of this segment and contribute in nation building.

b. Indian Public sector banks: Not for sole aim of profit, but for nation building and empowering the needy and the priority sector

As I have explained earlier the banking sector in India is not your regular job, it is more of a vocation or calling. A bank officer is posted anywhere across the length and breadth of the country. They have to sustain themselves on a meager salary when compared to other government jobs and are expected to perform their duties 24/7. There is no fixed working hour, with most working for 15-16 hours minimum in a day. In all this they are expected to perform their normal banking duties as well as cross-selling insurance, mutual funds and other non-banking related products. As such they are already over-worked, over-burdened and under-staffed. The bank officers on the branch level also have to complete different targets based on assets and liabilities and also recover NPAs. These officers are also the cream of the Indian society with their personal aims and ambitions. As such they inherit from their seniors certain misconceptions and prejudices as well as their own thought processes which consider rural postings as punishment-postings. It is a well known fact that the officers and staff who fail to meet the expected standards or are not particularly well connected with their bosses are usually sent for rural postings. As such we have many people who don't want to work in rural areas being sent to rural branches. In these circumstances it is but logical that disgruntled employees will not be able to perform their optimum with regards to priority sector advances and projects.

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We also have to note that most of our priority sector loans go bad (NPAs) due to the political factor. As most of our agriculture depends on rain, the climatic factor also plays a decisive role in success of crops and loan repayment thereon. Similarly with agriculture and MSMEs the finished products are unable to fetch the deserved prices due to middlemen and corporate manipulating the markets. This I have already explained in the same chapter.

And so, keeping in mind all these factors in addition to the manipulating of figures by corporate to push the blame of increasing NPAs on priority sector (explained in chapter 1), I strongly advocate that while profit can be one of the aspect of deciding the worthiness of the bank, it should not be made the sole criteria for deciding on the future of the public sector banks. Like other sectors banks need to be given incentives for their work of nation building and their contribution needs to be acknowledged by the general public.

c. A new benchmark financial model for the developing countries- not Socialist, nor Islamic, but pan-human

I conclude this paper with this statement, ‘The liberation philosophy of Marxist economy and its application to Shariah banking system will setup a new benchmark in banking for the developing economies around the world’. It will use the unique features of the liberation philosophy of Karl Marx and the community banking principles of the Shariah banking to create a unique model of commercial banking which will be based on a solid foundation of ethics and practical philosophy which transcends the academic theoretical boundaries to real life changing principles. This new model of banking could be utilized by Secular countries like India and also those which are neither Socialist, nor Islamic as it is a philosophy which advocates human good before all else. This is because we will take up from these philosophies the qualities which are universal and not dogmatic. For this a group of intellectuals, academics and finance professionals must be selected from across the nation and the world if possible to draft a constitution for this new model of banking. This banking model will not replace the existing commercial banks in India but will instead complement them by providing a solid foundation for engaging in banking for empowerment of the marginalized and the needy. In this system, I advocate that the bank will be in the nodal agency as in center of a web, coordinating the activities of different academic institutions, research organizations, government agencies and non-government organizations with those of farmers and MSMEs. Banks in this system will not wash away their hands after disbursement of loans but provide the necessary handholding and training till the marketing of the end products. Hence, they will be involved actively in the program of lending loans till its

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successful repayment. In this model, the rate of NPAs will reduce as there will be lesser chance of divergence of funds and wrong decisions by farmers due to lack of knowledge. It will also help in coordinating the sale of produce with the help of warehouse owners and commodity exchange platforms like the NCDEX, MCX at a market rate with a minimum cost of production limit so that the middlemen and corporate don't cheat the farmers. In-fact it will make the role of middlemen redundant in the new economic system with the farmers selling their produce directly to the wholesaler or even in some cases; directly to the consumer. Similarly the MSMEs will also be helped with a platform to showcase and sale their goods with the help of online trading apps and organizing various trade fairs so that industries and wholesalers will get an opportunity to see and verify their products and order directly from the MSMEs. All this is possible only if we imbibe the Marxist-Shariah model of ethics in our banking which will inculcate the individual and communitarian responsibility towards our own marginalized brethren. It will come as a huge morale booster not only for the marginalized and needy farmers and entrepreneurs but also for the bank employees, making them aware of their interdependencies on each other. It will eradicate the hierarchical vertical of bankers and consumers and replace it with a equal footing for all model where no one is superior or inferior to the other.

Hence, I conclude that the introduction of the Liberation Philosophy in Marxian Economics and its application to Shariah Banking to Indian Banking System will make it more ethical and contribute immensely to the need of nation building by energizing and revitalizing the priority sector as well as the banking sector (Saldanha, 2023).

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